

HyDelta 4

D4a.2 – Further exploration of balancing options and system design

Status: final version

Document summary

Corresponding author

Corresponding author	Sander Blom; Ryvo Octaviano; Rob van Zoelen
Affiliation	TNO and NEC
Email address	sander.blom@tno.nl ; ryvo.octaviano@tno.nl ; r.vanzoelen@newenergycoalition.org

Document history

Version	Date	Author	Affiliation	Summary of main changes
1	31-Mar-2026	Sander Blom	TNO	80% version
2	04-May-2026	Sander Blom	TNO	95% version
3	27-May-2026	Sander Blom	TNO	Final version for SG review

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
RE	Restricted to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project partners including Expert Assessment Group External entity with whom a Non-Disclosure Agreement exists 	

Document review

Partner	Name
Expert Advisory Group WP4a	Pascal te Morsche, Thijs Duisters, Quirine Wildeman, Edward Droste, Arjen Jongepier, Joyce Wiersma, Tom Eijsackers, Rudi Hakvoort, Rick Janssen, Holger Neef
NBNL, Gasunie, Kiwa, DNV, TNO, NEC	HyDelta Supervisory Group

Executive summary

Within the energy transition, hydrogen is gradually taking on a recognised role as a system-level energy carrier, which is now materialising in the first regional hydrogen networks across the Netherlands. Current developments show that these first hydrogen grid initiatives are predominantly organised as project-based systems, in which balancing is arranged through case-specific, bilateral solutions. While this approach fits the initial phase of market development, it raises structural challenges as the system scales: fragmented arrangements can limit market accessibility for new entrants, obscure cost structures, and create uncertainties and lock-ins that can delay investment decisions and inhibit broader market deployment. From a policy and system perspective, this creates a clear rationale to take a coordinated approach to balancing. This raises the question of how balancing should evolve from a project-specific activity to a more structured system that both facilitates market development and relieves individual projects, while preserving flexibility and enabling future scaling and integration.

This report presents the second phase of the HyDelta programme research on balancing regional hydrogen distribution grids. Where phase 1 established the conceptual foundation by defining balancing functionalities, grid archetypes, roles, and key knowledge gaps, this phase takes the next step by further exploring these gaps and further substantiating the framework with technical aspects and market perspectives. This report adds insight into how current initiatives and market parties view balancing in practice, which flexibility options and balancing instruments appear feasible, how response-time requirements shape the design of balancing regimes, and what changes when regional grids become coupled to the national hydrogen system.

In the short term, the development of balancing regimes must match the reality of the first regional hydrogen projects. Most initiatives are still organised around bi- or multilateral arrangements between a limited number of parties, and project-specific solutions rather than fully regulated open-access grids. In this stage, balancing is expected to depend primarily on portfolio balancing by trading parties, heavily dependent on the flexibility of connected assets, and a careful matching of supply and demand profiles. Hybrid set-ups at industrial offtakers, adjustable feed-in assets, and decentralized storage can provide important flexibility, while if a public DSO will be assigned for hydrogen distribution,¹ it has a safeguarding role and should intervene only when system integrity is at risk. Additionally, for many regional grids in the short term, required response times will be very short, meaning that automation, fast monitoring, and clearly defined escalation procedures are essential.

In the longer term, the transition from stand-alone regional grids to coupling with the national hydrogen network creates new possibilities for balancing. A larger system can provide access to broader flexibility, greater liquidity, and potentially more standardised market arrangements. At the same time, a system coupling introduces new design choices around portfolio balancing coordination, cost allocation, operational responsibilities, hydrogen quality requirements, and data exchange between customers, DSO and TSO. Three approaches are explored: pressure-controlled balancing, separate portfolio balancing regimes, and a central portfolio balancing regime. Based on current insights, the report points to separate balancing regimes as the most practical starting point

¹ Note that at time of publication no public DSO was officially assigned (yet) for hydrogen distribution. The archetypes used in this study assume that hydrogen distribution grids will be operated by a public DSO.

for many regional grids, while keeping open the possibility of moving towards a more centralised regime over time.

The main conclusion is that a harmonised balancing design for hydrogen distribution grids is possible, but that its practical implementation must reflect the phased development of the market. In early grids, balancing will depend much more on flexible portfolios, contractual arrangements, and the physical responsiveness of connected assets than on sophisticated market mechanisms. DSOs must be able to monitor the system continuously and apply escalation measures when needed, but they are not expected to solve routine balancing through technical intervention alone. Over time, standardisation of roles, interfaces, data exchange, and balancing principles becomes increasingly important, especially if regional grids are to scale up and connect smoothly to the national system.

Important knowledge gaps and challenges remain. These include uncertainty about the future regulatory framework and the legal boundaries of DSO intervention and flexibility procurement; limited insight into the required back-office, organisational setup, and costs of balancing arrangements; uncertainty about which market parties will take on trading and balancing roles in practice; and the need for further validation of response times, operational requirements, and feasible balancing arrangements across a wider variety of grid configurations. In addition, future decisions on system coupling will require clearer shared perspectives from DSOs, the TSO, regulators, and market parties on the desired long-term end-state of hydrogen balancing.

This ultimately leads to several recommendations for the parties involved:

1. Balancing should be addressed jointly and early in regional hydrogen projects, with DSOs, trading parties, and connected parties developing a shared understanding of roles, flexibility needs, and contractual arrangements.
2. Near-term balancing regimes should remain practical and scalable, relying on bilateral and portfolio-based solutions while avoiding design choices that block future standardisation.
3. Market parties should prepare early for balancing responsibilities by developing realistic portfolio strategies, securing contractual access to flexibility, and making clear arrangements on nominations, deviations, and emergency response.
4. Trading parties should focus on building portfolios that combine sufficient low-cost flexibility with predictable supply and demand profiles, so that balancing can be managed commercially before DSO intervention becomes necessary.
5. Regulators and policymakers should provide timely clarity on roles, responsibilities, and access rules, so that market parties can invest and participate with greater confidence while local solutions can still evolve towards a coherent wider hydrogen balancing framework over time.

The key next step is to develop a shared roadmap for hydrogen balancing, in which DSOs, TSO, market parties, and policymakers jointly define the transition towards a more standardised and scalable balancing framework. Active participation of all stakeholders is essential, with both market parties and policymakers contributing to and aligning around this roadmap. A coordinated approach will reduce uncertainty and provide a clear pathway for regulation, investment and system integration.

Samenvatting

Binnen de energietransitie krijgt waterstof geleidelijk een erkende systeemrol, wat zich inmiddels concreet manifesteert in de eerste regionale waterstofnetwerken in Nederland. Huidige ontwikkelingen laten zien dat deze eerste netten voornamelijk zijn georganiseerd als projectspecifieke systemen, waarin balancering plaatsvindt door maatwerk en bilaterale oplossingen. Hoewel deze aanpak past bij de beginfase van marktontwikkeling, brengt het structurele uitdagingen met zich mee naarmate het systeem opschaalt: uiteenlopende benaderingen kunnen een toegangdrempel vormen voor nieuwe toetreders, kostenstructuren minder transparant maken en onzekerheid creëren die investeringsbeslissingen kan vertragen. Vanuit beleids- en systeemperspectief ontstaat daardoor een duidelijke aanleiding om balancering meer gecoördineerd te organiseren. Dit roept de vraag op hoe balancering zich kan ontwikkelen van een projectspecifieke activiteit naar een meer gestructureerde systeemfunctie die zowel marktontwikkeling faciliteert als individuele projecten ontlast, terwijl flexibiliteit behouden blijft en verdere opschaling en integratie mogelijk zijn.

Dit rapport presenteert de onderzoeksresultaten van de tweede fase van het HyDelta-programma over balancering in regionale waterstofdistributienetten. Waar fase 1 de conceptuele basis heeft gelegd door functionaliteiten, archetypen, rollen en belangrijkste kennisgaten te definiëren, zet deze fase de volgende stap door deze kennisgaten verder te verkennen en het raamwerk verder te onderbouwen met technische aspecten en marktinzichten. Het rapport biedt inzicht in hoe huidige initiatieven en marktpartijen in de praktijk naar de balanceringsopgave kijken, welke flexibiliteitsopties en balanceringsinstrumenten haalbaar lijken, hoe vereisten aan de responstijd de inrichting van balanceringsregimes beïnvloeden en wat verandert wanneer regionale netten worden gekoppeld aan het nationale waterstofsysteem.

Op de korte termijn moet de ontwikkeling van balanceringsregimes aansluiten bij de realiteit van de eerste regionale waterstofprojecten. De meeste initiatieven zijn nog georganiseerd rond bilaterale afspraken tussen een beperkt aantal partijen en projectspecifieke oplossingen, in plaats van volledig gereguleerde netten met open toegang. In deze fase zal balancering naar verwachting voornamelijk afhangen van portfoliobalancering door handelspartijen, sterk afhankelijk van de flexibiliteit van aangesloten assets en een zorgvuldige afstemming van vraag- en aanbodprofielen. Hybride opstellingen bij industriële afnemers, regelbare invoeding en decentrale opslag kunnen in belangrijke mate flexibiliteit leveren, terwijl de mogelijk publieke regionale netbeheerder voor waterstof² primair een borgende rol vervult en alleen ingrijpt wanneer de systeemintegriteit in het geding is. Daarnaast geldt voor veel regionale netten op korte termijn dat de vereiste responstijden zeer kort kunnen zijn, waardoor automatisering, snelle monitoring en duidelijk gedefinieerde escalatieprocedures essentieel zijn.

Op de langere termijn biedt de overgang van stand-alone regionale netten naar koppeling met het nationale waterstofnet nieuwe mogelijkheden voor balancering. Een groter systeem kan toegang bieden tot bredere flexibiliteit, hogere liquiditeit en mogelijk meer gestandaardiseerde marktregelingen. Tegelijkertijd brengt een systeemkoppeling nieuwe ontwerpkeuzes met zich mee rond de coördinatie van portfoliobalancering, kostenallocatie, operationele verantwoordelijkheden, vereisten aan waterstofkwaliteit en dataverkeer tussen DSB en TSB. Drie regimes worden onderzocht: drukgestuurde balancering, gescheiden portfoliobalanceringsregimes en een centraal

² Op het moment van publiceren van deze studie is (nog) geen officiële publieke waterstof distributienetbeheerder aangewezen. Een van de veronderstellingen in de gebruikte archetypen is dat de regionale waterstofnetten door een publieke netbeheerder worden beheerd.

portfoliobalanceringsregime. Op basis van huidige inzichten wordt gewezen op gescheiden balanceringsregimes als het meest praktische startpunt voor veel regionale netten, terwijl de mogelijkheid open blijft om op termijn te groeien naar een meer gecentraliseerd regime.

De belangrijkste conclusie is dat een geharmoniseerd balanceringsontwerp voor waterstof distributienetten mogelijk is, maar dat de praktische implementatie moet aansluiten bij de gefaseerde ontwikkeling van de markt. In de eerste netten zal balancering sterker afhangen van flexibele portfolio's, contractuele afspraken en de flexibiliteit van aangesloten assets dan van geavanceerde centrale marktmechanismen. Netbeheerders moeten het systeem continu kunnen monitoren en waar nodig ingrijpen om de veiligheid te borgen, maar hoofdzakelijk zal de balanceringsverantwoordelijkheid van marktpartijen zijn. Naarmate het systeem zich ontwikkelt, wordt standaardisatie van rollen, interfaces, data-uitwisseling en balanceringsprincipes steeds belangrijker, met name als regionale netten willen opschalen en een koppeling aan het nationale systeem binnen bereik komt.

Belangrijke kennisgaten en uitdagingen blijven bestaan. Deze betreffen onder meer onzekerheid over het toekomstige regulatoire kader en de juridische grenzen van DSO-interventie en inkoop van flexibiliteit; beperkt inzicht in de benodigde backoffice, organisatorische inrichting en kosten van balanceringsmaatregelen; onzekerheid over welke marktpartijen in de praktijk handels- en balanceringsrollen op zich nemen; en de noodzaak om responstijden, operationele vereisten en haalbare balanceringsregelingen verder te valideren voor een bredere variëteit aan netconfiguraties. Daarnaast vergen toekomstige beslissingen over de inrichting van systeemkoppelingen een duidelijker gezamenlijk beeld van DSB's, de TSB, toezichhouders en marktpartijen over de gewenste eindsituatie voor waterstofbalancing.

Dit leidt tot verschillende aanbevelingen voor betrokken partijen:

1. Balancing dient vroegtijdig en gezamenlijk te worden opgepakt in regionale waterstofprojecten, waarbij DSB's, handelspartijen en aangesloten partijen een gedeeld begrip ontwikkelen van rollen, flexibiliteitsbehoeften en contractuele afspraken.
2. Balanceringsregimes moeten op korte termijn praktisch en schaalbaar blijven, door te bouwen op bilaterale en portfolio-gebaseerde oplossingen zonder toekomstige standaardisatie te belemmeren.
3. Marktpartijen moeten zich tijdig voor te bereiden op hun balanceringsverantwoordelijkheden door realistische portfoliostrategieën te ontwikkelen, contractuele toegang tot flexibiliteit te borgen en duidelijke afspraken te maken over nominaties, afwijkingen en noodprocedures.
4. De nadruk ligt voor handelspartijen op het opbouwen van portfolio's met voldoende kostenefficiënte flexibiliteit en voorspelbare vraag- en aanbodprofielen, zodat balancing primair commercieel kan worden ingevuld voordat ingrijpen door de DSO nodig is.
5. Het is van belang dat toezichhouders en beleidsmakers tijdig duidelijkheid bieden over rollen, verantwoordelijkheden en toegangsregels, zodat marktpartijen met meer zekerheid kunnen investeren en participeren, terwijl lokale oplossingen zich in de tijd kunnen ontwikkelen richting een samenhangend nationaal kader voor waterstofbalancing.

De belangrijkste vervolgstap is het ontwikkelen van een gezamenlijke roadmap voor waterstofbalancing, waarin DSO's, TSO, marktpartijen en beleidsmakers gezamenlijk de transitie naar een meer gestandaardiseerd en schaalbaar balanceringskader vormgeven. Actieve deelname van alle betrokken partijen is hierbij essentieel, waarbij zowel marktpartijen als beleidsmakers

bijdragen en zich committeren aan deze roadmap. Een gecoördineerde aanpak vermindert onzekerheid en biedt een duidelijk perspectief voor investeringen en systeemintegratie.

Table of contents

Document summary	2
Executive summary	3
Samenvatting.....	5
1. Introduction.....	10
2. Starting point: lessons from phase 1 to knowledge gaps phase 2	11
2.1 Balancing regional hydrogen grids: terminology	11
2.2 Portfolio balancing and system balancing	12
2.3 Regional hydrogen grid archetypes	13
2.4 Functionalities of a hydrogen balancing system.....	13
2.5 Research gaps and methodology	14
Flexibility and Balancing in Stand-alone Regional Grids.....	15
3. Grid developments and market needs.....	16
3.1 Stakeholder discussions – description and approach.....	16
3.2 Flexibility needs of regional hydrogen grids	18
4. Technical aspects of market flexibility and balancing instruments	20
4.1 Flexibility options of market parties	21
4.2 Technical aspects of system balancing options	24
5. Balancing instruments.....	26
5.1 A set of balancing instruments for archetype 1-3 grids.....	26
5.2 Requirements to design balancing enabling mechanisms.....	30
6. Response times of balancing instruments	33
6.1 Response time ranges.....	33
6.2 Balancing chains of actions and associated times	34
6.3 Impact of varying response times.....	39
6.4 Conclusions on the impact of response time scales	41
From Regional to National Integration.....	42
7. System coupling of DSO and TSO: three balancing approaches.....	43
System coupling of DSO and TSO networks	43
Three approaches for portfolio balancing after system coupling.....	43
Selecting the balancing regime	45
8. Considerations for system coupling	45
System coupling costs	45
Flexibility and competition.....	46
Conclusion on the system coupling decision.....	46

Operation of a system coupling	46
Buffer vessels and decentralized storage.....	47
Contracts for system balancing	47
Access for trading and connected parties.....	47
Market and price mechanisms	48
Data and monitoring	48
Intermediate conclusions	48
Key Findings and Way Forward	50
9. Conclusions.....	51
10. Remaining knowledge gaps and challenges.....	53
11. Recommendations per party.....	54
11.1 Recommendations for policy makers, market participants and DSO	54
11.2 Recommendations for policy makers.....	55
11.3 Recommendations for trading parties and connected parties	55
11.4 Recommendations for the distribution system operator (DSO)	56
11.5 Next steps.....	56
References.....	57
Appendices	58
A. Indicative flexibility needs based on potential entry and exit customers.....	58
B. Detailed information on market flexibility options.....	61
Flexibility of electrolysis depending on regulation, subsidy and electricity grid services.....	61
Considerations for flexibility options on the exit side.....	62
Merit order and cost indications for market flexibility options	63
C. Technical tools for the DSO: incremental valves and storage.....	66
D. Description of the concept set of balancing instruments	76
From balancing functions to a set of instruments	76
1. Balancing instruments.....	77
2. Supportive instruments.....	78
Reflection on the set of instruments.....	79

1. Introduction

As hydrogen is expected to play a pivotal role in the Dutch energy transition, adequate infrastructure is needed to safely and efficiently connect hydrogen supply, storage, and demand. Alongside the plans for the national hydrogen infrastructure being developed by Hynetwork, the first regional hydrogen grids are being planned and developed to serve regional hydrogen offtakers (e.g. Cluster 6 industry), which may be operated by Dutch distribution system operators (DSOs). Users of these regional hydrogen grids will benefit from low-threshold access to a reliable and well-functioning distribution system. A fundamental component of such a hydrogen grid is a robust balancing regime to ensure that supply and demand are safely balanced, and system integrity is maintained.

In the first part of this research, suitable balancing regime elements for regional hydrogen grids were identified based on experiences in electricity and gas systems, explicit functionalities that must be present in the balancing system were specified, different scenarios of role distribution among relevant parties were explored and key knowledge gaps were identified. These knowledge gaps are further explored in the second part of this research, expanding on aspects that were previously addressed at a high level.

The key knowledge gaps determined at the end of the first stage were formulated into the following research questions at the outset of the second stage:

- What is the market perspective on the balancing framework established in the first stage, and what barriers do current projects face with respect to balancing?
- What are the consequences of different response times for balancing functionalities from the technical and market perspective?
- What is the expected availability and feasibility of flexibility and balancing instruments?
- What options are available for system balancing in case portfolio balancing is insufficient, and what technical operation strategy follows from that?
- How does an outlook towards coupling national and regional networks determine portfolio balancing systems and decisions regarding the system coupling?

To answer these questions, this report is divided into three parts. The first part focuses on stand-alone grids (archetypes 1-3 from the previous research). Here, (1) a market perspective and the identified needs based on current projects are presented, (2) available technical tools and options for flexibility are examined, (3) the required balancing instruments are identified and (4) the required time scales for these balancing instruments are analysed.

The second part examines the connection between regional grids and the national network, starting with (5) defining three possible approaches for coupling portfolio national and regional networks and their balancing regimes and concluding with (6) key considerations for system coupling.

2. Starting point: lessons from phase 1 to knowledge gaps phase 2

In the first part of this research, a balancing regime for regional hydrogen grids was scoped, with associated terminology, definitions, archetype description and functionalities. A brief summary of these concepts is given, as these terms are used throughout the report.

2.1 Balancing regional hydrogen grids: terminology

In this section, we will provide a brief list of relevant terminology that will be used to describe the proposed balancing regime for regional hydrogen grids. In some cases, the terminology overlaps with that used in the gas world and in other cases it is distinct. Further, we include here the corresponding term in Dutch to alleviate confusion.

Table 1: Relevant terminology to the regional hydrogen grid balancing regime. [1]

English term	Dutch term	Definition / Remarks
Trading party	Handelspartij	Entities that transport hydrogen on the network (equivalent to “shipper” in the GTS world). The term trading party is often adopted in lieu of Balance Responsible Party (BRP) or supplier (Dutch: leverancier) as the latter concerns the role defined in regulation, and the former the party that can take up that role. It is also not yet known whether the roles of BRP and supplier will be held by a single party or different parties. For these reasons, trading party is used to describe the responsibilities that fall under both roles in an attempt to maintain simplicity and allow for further specification. Additional guidance on how these roles will be assigned is expected to be provided in future legislation.
Connected party	Aangesloten	A party connected to the network via a connection capacity contracted with the DSO.
Feeder	Invoeder	A connected party that feeds hydrogen into the network (can include storage, imports, or connections with neighbouring networks).
Offtaker	Afnemer	A connected party that consumes hydrogen (can include storage).
Portfolio balancing	Portfoliobalancing	Actions taken by trading parties to maintain balance in their portfolios.
System balancing	Systeembalancing	Actions taken by the system operator to maintain grid integrity and resolve residual imbalance that is not handled by portfolio balancing.
Nominations	Nominaties	Information that a trading party must submit to the system operator (i.e., location-specific planned entry, exit, and trades (including counterparts) at a frequency that still must be determined (e.g.,

Portfolio	Handelsprogramma	hourly, 30-minute, 15-minute intervals) for the coming day of hydrogen delivery). ³ A collection of entry (in-feed) and exit (offtake) transactions (including trades) that relate to a single trading party. Each day, the trading party is expected to balance their portfolio and notify the system operator (day-ahead and within-day, if necessary) of their planned entry, exit, and trades for the coming hydrogen delivery day via a nomination (above).
Connection agreement	Aansluitovereenkomst (AO)	A contract between the DSO and a connected party that dictates the terms associated with connection capacity.
Transport agreement	Transportovereenkomst (TO)	A contract between the DSO and a trading party that dictates the terms associated with transport capacity.

2.2 Portfolio balancing and system balancing

The first phase report emphasizes that balancing encompasses two fundamental realms: system and portfolio balancing, as shown in Figure 1. These are two distinct domains in the current natural gas and electricity systems, with a clear separation of actions and responsible parties. Nonetheless, these two are expected to be much more intertwined in early-stage hydrogen grids, particularly due to limited flexibility options and an immature hydrogen market.

Figure 1: Distinction between portfolio and system balancing and their relationship to balancing as a whole. [1]

³ In the GTS system there is a distinction between *programmes* and *nominations*. Trading parties (i.e., shippers) have been historically required to submit both a programme (which were largely used to see if damping had been applied correctly but this is not expected to be relevant in most regional hydrogen grids for the foreseeable future **Ongeldige bron opgegeven**.) and a nomination to GTS. Nominations will effectively replace programmes in the GTS system in the future. Therefore, we adopt the term *nominations* to refer to all information that a trading party must submit to the system operator regarding their planned entry, exit, and trades.

2.3 Regional hydrogen grid archetypes

Since regional hydrogen grids are expected to take different forms and exhibit varying levels of complexity, the balancing requirements of these distinct grid configurations are expected to be unique from one another. As such, five regional hydrogen grid archetypes are identified to examine how balancing needs and functionalities differ across the various grid types (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Future archetypes of hydrogen distribution grids (note: not all grids will move sequentially from Archetype 1 to 5). [1]

- Archetype 1 consists of a single trading party and single feeder, with possibly multiple off-takers. It features a stand-alone distribution grid with simple, top-down flows and no expected transport integrity issues.
- Archetype 2 distinguishes itself from the first one by including multiple feeders, further complexifying flows on the network.
- Archetype 3 has multiple trading parties, allowing for more portfolio balancing actions through trade and coordination, while adding more variables and complexity at the same time.
- In archetypes 4 and 5, the regional grid connects to the Hynetwork system, either with a unidirectional flow from the national grid to the regional grid (4), or a bidirectional flow (5). Key considerations arise concerning balancing roles and responsibilities between DSO and TSO.

2.4 Functionalities of a hydrogen balancing system

It is expected that a comprehensive balancing strategy for regional hydrogen grids must contain the following components:

- A capacity booking process, constrained by network capacity, where trading parties reserve the rights to transport hydrogen on the DSO network.
- A process to facilitate the commercial matching of supply and demand via portfolio balancing (e.g., a trading platform to enable trade between trading parties, a penalty and incentive regime to encourage favourable balancing behaviour, etc.).
- Options for system balancing actions, which are needed to keep the system within its operating limits and safeguard network integrity (e.g., storage, making use of limited linepack, tapping into flexibility at feeders and off-takers through contract agreements and ultimately by direct control)
- An allocation and correction process to assign the costs of imbalance to the trading parties who are responsible for it (and potentially compensate those who improve balance in the network)

These components are laid out in eleven functionalities, defining the needs of a balancing system from years ahead to time of delivery. The functionalities are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Overview of balancing functionalities defined in phase 1. [1]

#	Functionality name
F1	Investment and maintenance of hydrogen infrastructure
F2	Assignment of transport capacity to trading parties
F3	Connecting feed-in and offtake - nominations
F4	Nomination review and confirmation
F5	Measurement and data management
F6	Maintaining transport capacity in real-time
F7	Real-time portfolio balancing
F8	Maintaining system integrity real-time
F9	Delivery – sales and purchases
F10	Allocation and correction
F11	Flexibility services

2.5 Research gaps and methodology

This report continues from the research gaps defined in the phase 1 report [1]. Based on the research gaps, new research questions are formulated and will be answered via different methodologies: literature research, interviews with existing initiatives and expert consultations and discussions. Given the immaturity of the topic and state of the literature, this research has a strongly exploratory character.

Part I

Flexibility and Balancing in Stand-alone Regional Grids

3. Grid developments and market needs

In the second stage of the project, stakeholder discussions were conducted to reflect on the findings of the first stage. These findings were a result of cooperation between network operators and research institutes, leaving market perspectives to be explored in a subsequent step. The stakeholder discussions provided insight into how market parties view the results, assumptions, and interpretations developed during phase 1, and helped position the analytical work within current market perspectives. Moreover, they provide a high-level overview of the status and progress of current projects.

This chapter provides impressions and findings from these stakeholder discussions. An effective balancing regime needs to fit current challenges and not constrain development towards future situations. As such, an overview of where current projects stand can help prioritize and identify current barriers.

3.1 Stakeholder discussions – description and approach

Participants of five regional hydrogen grid projects in development were interviewed to gather practical and market perspectives on balancing. These are projects where either a local hydrogen grid is already under construction, or that have a relatively mature plan to set up a hydrogen grid. These projects include:

- [H₂opper](#) (Delfzijl)
- [Startmotor](#) (Veendam)
- [H2avennet](#) (Amsterdam)
- [Kapelle](#)
- [GROHW](#) (Deventer)

The projects are currently thinking about the first phase of development where between two and four connected parties are expected to be present on the network, while the H2avennet project is already engaging with around ten potential connected parties. In some projects, one trading party was actively considering taking up the role of Balancing Responsible Party for other parties on the network. For these discussions, representatives of at least two market parties, and of the system operator involved in the project, were present.

Most projects are currently at a stage where balancing is currently arranged via bilateral agreements

The current phase of development of most of the projects discussed during the interviews, cannot be attributed to archetype 1 of the balancing framework, since there is not (yet) a regulated grid operator or regulated open-access situation. These projects typically take the form of point-to-point connections, or connection of (one or more) intermittent production assets to a flexible demand. A typical setup is the connection of an electrolyzer to an off-taker that can flexibly replace its natural gas input with hydrogen, providing flexibility and balancing in the first stage of these projects.

This situation makes the requirements of balancing the grid significantly less complex and is likely one of the reasons it has been designed this way, as a starting point. As a consequence, however, market insights into balancing roles, market dynamics and providing flexibility are difficult to derive from these discussions.

However, for one of the interviewed projects, multiple larger producers are expected to be connected to the network in the initial phase, delivering hydrogen to offtakers that do not necessarily blend hydrogen into a natural gas installation flexibly. In this network, consistent with archetype 1, it is immediately clear that balancing needs coordination between parties involved, and possibly a trading party taking up the role of BRP.

In most cases, the development of regional hydrogen grids appears to follow a stepwise approach, with bilateral contracts between producer and off-taker and point-to-point connections being a safe first step in the uncertainty surrounding hydrogen system development. Producers variably supplying multiple offtakers on a market-price-driven basis is not yet within sight. However, for initiatives that are already faced with multiple connected parties that need coordination of feed-in and offtake profiles, it is relevant for a (regulated) DSO to join an initiative.

Timely consideration of balancing is crucial in moving towards the next step

Nevertheless, balancing remains a central and highly important topic that needs to be addressed early on. The projects discussed during the interviews may have been focused on point-to-point connections at this time, but in almost all cases a larger and more complex mix of connected parties is foreseen in the next step. This includes multiple connected parties (moving towards archetype 1 and 2) and the potential addition of connected parties to the grid that have very variable production or off-take (e.g. an asphalt producer).

As the number of connected parties increases, hydrogen distribution grids will increasingly occupy public space. To avoid parallel grid infrastructures or the application of differing operational conditions within the same area, regulation of hydrogen distribution grids may become necessary. As these grids develop and expand, this calls for a more standardized and coherent approach to their design and operation. In general, a balancing design should match this phased way of thinking. It needs to simultaneously provide a robust and generalized design, fit for all grids and archetypes, while remaining useful and offering practical guidance for market parties in the earliest stages. It is therefore recommended to bring all participants together in a regional hydrogen grid at an early stage to jointly discuss balancing, using this explorative research as talking points. Early hydrogen grid projects are likely to require a project-specific balancing approach, with insights from these first applications then informing further harmonisation and standardisation at a broader level.

A trading party explicitly taking the role of Balancing Responsible Party is constructive to collaboration on balancing

The few projects interviewed that *are* already looking towards a next phase where multiple connected parties are present on the grid and balancing is more challenging, distinguish themselves from the rest in the role of a Balancing Responsible Party (BRP). Here, a trading party is present to take up this role, connecting feed-in and off-take within its portfolio and thinking ahead towards connecting parties in its portfolio or potential parties to be included.

From parties taking or foreseeing this role the most insight was gathered on obstacles of moving towards a next archetype, or feedback on the proposed balancing framework. In the end, all parties connected to a regional grid must either act as a BRP or be part of a BRP's portfolio. It is therefore advisable for the DSO to actively inform connected parties of these obligations and to help them either gain sufficient understanding of the balancing framework or explore options to participate via a trading party's portfolio.

3.2 Flexibility needs of regional hydrogen grids

When existing initiatives would move towards archetype 1-3 grids, a structured approach is needed to deploy flexibility needs. In the existing initiatives that were interviewed, it is seen that balancing is arranged via customized arrangements between the parties involved. These customized balancing arrangements are based on the specific flexibility needs and available flexibility options in that initiative. *Flexibility needs* here refer to the required ability to adjust feed-in or offtake to better align (expected) production and consumption profiles on a daily basis, distinct from balancing needs which address real-time imbalances and outages.

This situation changes when these grids become open-access, as assumed in archetypes 1-3. New connected parties being granted access to the grid could potentially complicate balancing, as in open-access grids the flexibility needs are determined by the parties that might connect to or disconnect from the grid.

Existing initiatives reveal that significant flexibility needs are covered by a diversity of flexibility options

In the initiatives covered by the interviews, significant flexibility needs were seen. Examples of these flexibility needs are:

- Electrolysers have a variable feed-in pattern based on renewable electricity availability, leading to significant flexibility needs;
- Hydrogen consumers requiring a stable baseload supply of hydrogen, leading to flexibility required elsewhere in the system, especially when present alongside other consumers and suppliers with variable patterns;
- Specific hydrogen consumer profiles with demand peaks, such as asphalt factories or consumption of hydrogen as a power back-up. These require significant flexible capacity to balance these peaks;
- Disruptions in supply or demand installations, leading to a general need for backup flexibility.

In most initiatives, part of this needed flexibility was foreseen to be delivered by hydrogen consumers that were able to switch towards alternative fuels, such as natural gas, electricity or grey hydrogen. There was one initiative where most of the flexibility is expected on the production side, instead of the consumption side. However, in most initiatives there is at least one consumer that keeps their natural gas grid connection, and often most of the consumers do so. As the consumed hydrogen volumes are initially small compared to the total energy consumption, the ability to blend 0-20% hydrogen behind the meter could often already provide significant flexibility for the hydrogen grid. In some of the initiatives other flexibility options were considered as well, namely:

- Hydrogen consumers able to scale up or down demand by 10-20%;
- Parties able to adapt their hydrogen injection, such as gasification, liquid hydrogen vaporization or ammonia cracking processes;
- Storage tanks. However, these alone are foreseen to be too small to cover the full flexibility needs.

The flexibility needs of future open-access distribution grids will depend on the combination of the parties connected

Archetypes 1-3 hydrogen distribution grids are defined as open access grids where one (archetype 1-2) or multiple (archetype 3) trading party(s) are in place as being responsible for balancing the portfolio(s) of entry and exit customers. This adds complexity over the situation in the existing initiatives (that may not yet qualify as archetype 1), as the system should be robust for new parties connecting or existing parties disconnecting from the grid.

In archetype 1-3 grids the trading party(s) are responsible for balancing their portfolio of entry and exit customers and therefore new entrants can only obtain and/or inject hydrogen into the grid if arrangements can be made with a trading party. The trading party should be able to balance its portfolio at any time. If the profile of the potential new entrant would not comply to the existing portfolio, the offer of the trading party could include significant costs for the potential new entrant, making the potential new entrant refrain from connecting to the grid. Hence, in this way it can be expected that the market will determine which combination of parties can be connected and probably also that certain combinations of parties might not be cost-efficient enough at this point in time.

An overview of the indicative flexibility needs based on potential entry and exit parties is provided in Appendix 7A. The flexibility options that can be utilized in this context are discussed in chapter 4. The information in these chapters will provide some high-level context in which combinations of parties might be more and less challenging to combine in one portfolio.

Summarized, the most critical flexibility needs relevant for portfolio optimization are:

- Potential connected parties that can represent significant volumes with variable profiles are electrolyzers (based on wind and/or solar electricity) on the entry side and asphalt, chemicals, paper, food and back-up power on the exit side. The combination of these connected parties may lead to the highest flexibility needs.⁴
- Potential entry and exit customers with baseload profiles are SMR and hydrogen carrier reconversion technologies on the entry side and chemicals, glass, ceramics and decentral metal industries on the exit side. These entry customers can adapt their injection based on demand. Grids with these exit customers in combination with variable electrolyzers will require flexibility as well.
- Biomass gasification can adapt its injection on a hourly or daily basis, but requires seasonal flexibility.
- All potential entry and exit customers are in risk of process disruptions, forecasting errors and systems going down. This requires back-up flexibility and/or procedures. The more the total volumes depend on one or a limited number of parties in the regional grid, the larger the needs for back-up flexibility and if not (technically or economically) available, then the higher the impact on the system if such a large customer is facing a disruption.

These flexibility needs directly impact the portfolio balancing requirements by the trading party(s). Therefore the flexibility options of market participants are discussed in the next chapter. Similarly, technical tools available for system balancing by the DSO are discussed, for instances in which the market is not able to keep the system in balance.

⁴ Note that some of these actors can deliver flexibility as well, however this will be analysed in chapter 4.

4. Technical aspects of market flexibility and balancing instruments

Market participants are responsible for balancing their own portfolios (portfolio balancing). If individual portfolios are not adequately balanced and this affects overall system stability, the DSO may intervene to maintain system balance (system balancing). In this chapter both the flexibility options of market participants and the technical aspects of hydrogen grid balancing are discussed.

In hydrogen distribution networks, pressure is a key indicator of system balance. A typical operating range for a regional grid (e.g. H2avennet) could be 8–16 bar, where 8 bar is the minimum safe operating pressure and 16 bar is the maximum. Some regional grids may also operate at pressures of 4–8 bar, which result in a lower linepack capacity and a faster balancing response required. These pressure ranges are too limited to subdivide flexibility among customers, unlike the national network, where Hynetwork foresees this being possible.

Imbalances are therefore managed by assigning roles to market participants (trading parties). If balance cannot be maintained by the market, the DSO needs to intervene by applying specific technical solutions. The pressure range can be divided into four zones, using a color-coded system:

Pressure zone	Pressure range	Role	System Balancing Tools
Normal operating zone	10–14 bar	Trading party(s)	Portfolio balancing (market participants adjust injection/withdrawal), within the operational margin provided by available linepack.
Mild deviation	9–10 bar and 14–15 bar	Trading party(s) and DSO	Trading party(s) requested to adjust portfolios; DSO may prepare incremental valve adjustment or local storage if needed
Moderate deviation	8–9 bar and 15–16 bar	DSO	DSO could activate incremental valves at supplier/consumer connections; may use local storage to absorb or inject hydrogen
Critical	≤ 8 bar and ≥ 16 bar	DSO	Emergency system balancing at DSO connection: shut-off valve to protect system integrity of the pipeline.

This chapter begins with chapter 4.1, which explores the flexibility options of connected parties that can be utilized by trading parties to maintain portfolio balance. The principle is that most of the balancing should be organized by the market (portfolio balancing). If the DSO measures that pressure levels are going outside predefined levels, there are system balancing instruments that it can utilize. The technical details of these are described in chapter 4.2.

4.1 Flexibility options of market parties

Flexibility options exist on both entry and exit sides. Trading parties face the challenge of attracting a suitable portfolio with sufficient low-cost flexibility providers. The degree in which future potential open access archetype 1-3 grids are able to grow towards initiatives with a larger number of participants likely depends on the availability of connected parties that can deliver flexibility at acceptable costs. If potentially new connected parties would lead to expected situations where balancing needs to be performed with flexibility options of >3000 EUR/MWh[2] or large decentralized storages with high leveled storage costs, this would result in an infeasible business case of starting to use hydrogen, and the new entrant would likely not be accepted.

Hence, trading party(s) will likely aim for a portfolio where the proportion of connected parties with relatively low cost of flexibility provision should be large enough to balance the ones with a large flexibility need. Given the characteristics analysed in this chapter and chapter 3.2, this means that connected parties with more flexibility needs than options, such as electrolysers and high-temperature heat offtakers in industry, can only be part of hydrogen distribution systems as long as enough connected parties with more flexibility options than needs are available. These connected parties include hybrid hydrogen consumers and feeders that can flexibly adapt their injection.

The following subchapters will discuss the flexibility options of potential exit and entry parties in greater detail, including cost indications for these options.

Flexibility options on entry side are found mainly in SMR, gasification, hydrogen carrier reconversion and storage assets

An overview of entry side flexibility options was already provided in phase 1 of this research [1]. The conclusion was that most entry side technologies are able to ramp up and ramp down in the range of minutes, and that PEM electrolysis even is able to ramp up and down in seconds (see Table 3). However, despite electrolysis being technically able to ramp up and down very quickly, the business case to do so is heavily determined by RFNBO requirements, subsidy requirements and the degree to which the electrolyser is aiming to provide balancing or congestion services for the electricity grid. More information on this is provided in Appendix B.

Decentralized hydrogen storage in tanks was not yet included in the overview in phase 1. Decentral hydrogen storages are in fact able to feed-in with very fast response times within seconds, if hydrogen is available in the facility.

Table 3: Start-up times and ramp rates for different hydrogen distribution grid entry technologies [1]

Type	Cold Start up	Ramp rates
Alkaline electrolyzer [3]	1 hour	±18% / minute
PEM electrolyzer [3]	10 minutes	±10% / second
AEM electrolyzer [3]	30 minutes	+28% / minute, -10% / seconds
Steam Methane Reforming (SMR)	15 hours	±3% / minute
Biomass gasification [4]	1 day	+3% / minute, - 5% / minute
Ammonia cracking [5]	1 day	±3% / minute
Methanol cracking [6]	20 minutes	±4.9% / minute

Vaporization liquid hydrogen	-	instantaneous
Decentral hydrogen tank storage	-	Flexible / seconds

Flexibility options on exit side are mostly found in assets not directly impacting primary, non-energy related processes of the consumer

For flexibility options on the exit side, it is important to distinguish two types of demand side flexibility [2]:

- Energy system related: not directly coupled to the primary process of the offtaker
- Primary process related: directly coupled to the primary process of the offtaker

It is important to consider this difference because adaptations in energy system related assets do not impact a primary industrial production process of the offtaker. These assets are decoupled from the primary process, due to their ability to switch between fuels, store energy or if the primary activity of this asset is to deliver value to the energy system. This leaves room for optimization and short term reactions with less severe consequences to daily operation of industrial processes. If the flexibility options affect a primary (non-energy related) process, often quite strong reasons or financial incentives need to be in place to adapt the production schedule of an industrial plant, for example.

Still, these second category of processes can be decoupled from the primary process by energy system related assets, such as, for example, adding gaseous hydrogen storage at an exit customer. Adding dual fuel optionality is not of similar ease for different types of exit parties. For example, processes where the flames from the burners are in direct contact with the end product. This means that the flame characteristics, which change if (varying) blends of natural gas and hydrogen would be used, do impact the quality and characteristics of the products (e.g. glass, bricks, metals, etc.) produced.

Examples of energy system related options are dual fuel boilers, hybrid CHP, heat buffers, hybrid heat pumps and H₂ storage (see Table 4). Typically, these can react relatively quickly. Examples of primary-process related flexibility are production batch rescheduling or increasing/decreasing/stopping continuous processes (see Table 5). The reaction times for these processes are typically slower and often costly, especially for continuous high temperature industries such as glass and ceramics. See Appendix B for more detailed considerations on the flexibility options of exit parties.

Table 4: Potential energy system related flexibility options at exit points of hydrogen distribution grids

Type	Cold Start up	Ramp rates
Hybrid hydrogen/natural gas boiler	1-5 hours	Seconds - minutes
Hybrid hydrogen/natural gas CHP	10-30 minutes	Seconds - minutes
Hydrogen (industrial) boiler combined with heat buffer storage	Depending on hydrogen industrial boiler (see above)	Depending on hydrogen industrial boiler, minutes – 10 minutes
Hybrid electricity/hydrogen driven heat pump	Depending on hydrogen	Depending on hydrogen component, minutes – 10 minutes

	component (see above)	
Existing hydrogen consumers that start (partial) consumption of (green) hydrogen from the grid	N.A.	Seconds - minutes
Decentral hydrogen tank storage	-	Depending on compressor capacity, can be seconds
Hybrid FCEV and HCEV driven vehicles	-	Charging reaction times in seconds, but depending on charging behaviour: hours-days

Table 5: Potential primary process related flexibility options at exit points of hydrogen distribution grids

Sector	Type of process	Flex option	Time to scale up/down
Concrete	Kilns are continuous, drying is batch	Scheduling	Unknown
Asphalt	Primary batch processes in the Netherlands	Scheduling	Unknown
Chemical	Continuous	In/decrease	6-24 hours
Paper	Batch processes	Scheduling	24 hours – 1 week
Food	Batch processes	Scheduling	1-8 hours
Glass	Continuous	In/decrease	>12 hours – weeks
Ceramics	Continuous	In/decrease	>12 hours – weeks
Metal	Batch processes	Scheduling	1-6 hours
Greenhouse	CHP (often including heat storage)	Flexible	Seconds – minutes

Mobility / HRS Hydrogen tube-filling station	Service process Potentially flexible based on market situations or baseload	Planning Flexible	Hours – days Seconds - minutes
--	---	-------------------	--------------------------------

Hybrid hydrogen consumers and adjustable feed-in are likely the most cost-effective flexibility options, optionally supported by decentralized storage for short-term flexibility

Despite the fact that indicative estimations on the marginal and integral costs of the different flexibility options can be provided, it is not straightforward to forecast which flexibility options would be prioritized for balancing in archetype 1-3 hydrogen distribution grids. This hugely depends on the following aspects:

- Which actors, characteristics and assets are present in the hydrogen distribution grid;
- Design of balancing instruments and contractual agreements between different entities;
- Actual energy market circumstances, costs of assets and interventions.

However, based on the merit order and integral cost insights in Appendix B and the flexibility options foreseen in several of the existing initiatives, the trend seems to be that archetype 1-3 hydrogen grid initiatives are formed around a couple of industrial consumers that are willing to decarbonize by (partially) starting to use low carbon hydrogen. In those cases it is seen that some of these industrial consumers are able to absorb variable feed-in of electrolyzers in a cost-effective manner, for example by hybrid offtake of the low carbon hydrogen in combination with an alternative fuel, such as natural gas⁵, electricity or grey hydrogen.

In a couple of cases the volumes and flexibility could be expanded by SMR, gasification or hydrogen carrier reconversion entry parties that are able to deliver more stable and partially adjustable feed-in flows. Hence, it seems likely that the flexibility in first initiatives should be searched in this direction, potentially in combination with decentral hydrogen storage to balance short-term deviations.

4.2 Technical aspects of system balancing options

When the system turns out to be not in balance by portfolio balancing, the DSO has system balancing options disposal to intervene. In practice, short-term imbalances can occur due to measurement errors, forecasting errors, disruptions, sudden demand changes, or fluctuations and malfunctions in hydrogen production. When market participants are not able to resolve these imbalances quickly enough through portfolio balancing, the DSO has several technical options to maintain system balance and integrity.

Linepack contributes to short-term buffering but does not function as a balancing instrument

Linepack refers to the temporary storage of hydrogen within pipelines by slightly adjusting the pressure in the system. When supply is higher than demand, the pressure in the network increases and additional hydrogen is stored in the pipelines. When demand increases, the stored hydrogen can

⁵ These hydrogen offtakers will therefore likely retain their natural gas network connection for a significant amount of time, showing the need for roll-out of new infrastructure as opposed to being able to re-use natural gas infrastructure.

be released as the pressure decreases. The available linepack that can be used for balancing in DSO grids is limited due to the limited operational pressure range and the pressure drop in the system.

Therefore it is most likely that in distribution grids linepack will be used to absorb shocks and allow for time to respond to imbalance incidents, rather than using it as a balancing instrument or flexibility resource for market parties.

System balancing tools are flexible but should not be used for routine balancing

These tools allow the operator to temporarily manage supply-demand mismatches and maintain stable pressure and flow conditions in the network. The main technical balancing options available to a DSO include:

1. Contractual arrangements for supply and demand intervention

Some connected parties may have the ability to adjust their hydrogen production or consumption. These options are similar to the options described in chapter 4.1. It is possible for the DSO and connected parties to make arrangements on (part of this) flexibility being used for system balancing. The same technical aspects as described before apply.

2. Deployment of flexibility services

If contractual arrangements are not possible or available, the deployment of flexibility services is an available system balancing tool. A likely flexibility service provider would be a storage operator. Dedicated hydrogen storage connected to the distribution network can provide additional flexibility for balancing the system by absorbing excess hydrogen when supply is high and release hydrogen back into the grid when demand increases.

Storage can be located at different points in the network, such as: hydrogen production sites, large industrial consumers, strategic nodes in the distribution grid. Storage of hydrogen can be performed with gaseous hydrogen or via hydrogen carriers, in this study only technical concepts for gaseous hydrogen storage at pipeline pressure level and high pressure level were assessed.

It can also be considered that the DSO is eligible to manage and operate storage facilities themselves. For grids with a challenging balancing situation, this situation becomes more desirable.

3. Incremental Flow Limitation at Connection Points

At the connection points of suppliers and consumers, incremental control valves can be used to gradually limit the hydrogen flow when necessary. These valves allow the DSO to intervene in the nominated profile to reduce the flow gradually instead of completely shutting off the connection. A warning is first issued to the connected party, after which the valve is gradually closed.

4. Shut-off Valve at Connection Points

At the connection, a shut-off valve is used to protect the pipeline when system integrity is at risk as an emergency action. This is a last-resort action for system integrity and comes with significant impact to connected parties and associated costs.

In the second phase of this project, the technical aspects of two technical tools that support system balancing by the DSO have been worked out in greater detail: **incremental valves** at connection points and **hydrogen storage** connected to the distribution network. The relevant details of these two technical balancing tools of the DSO are discussed in appendix C.

5. Balancing instruments

The way in which market flexibility options and technical aspects of the DSOs are structurally deployed for portfolio and system balancing is determined by the designed set of balancing instruments. Hence, balancing instruments are defined as *agreements and structured frameworks between the trading party(s), connected parties and DSO enabling to deploy flexibility options and technical aspects for the physical balancing of the grid.* Next to the general instruments that directly steer and relate to the flexibility options and technical aspects, there are also supportive instruments that *support by information sharing or preconditional clauses related to balancing.* As currently limited regulation is in place, there is still a lot of freedom in how this set of instruments can be designed. This means that these instruments do not necessarily need to be a reflection of existing practices in the electricity and natural gas worlds. Moreover, there will be significant freedom for market parties to agree and structure portfolio balancing.

A fundamental decision in the design choice is whether a standardized or customized set of instruments is desired per regional hydrogen grid.

Significant advantages of a standardized set of balancing instruments for all regional hydrogen grids are that development and maintenance costs of the balancing system can be shared and that procedures are equal and understandable for grid operator departments and market parties who work on multiple grids. A challenge with standardization is that a robust system design is required applicable to all the unique and situational characteristics of regional grids. Moreover, experiences with the electricity and natural gas balancing systems learn that these systems will develop and be adapted over time based on changing needs and requirements of the energy system. Changes in a standardized balancing system might have different (unexpected) implications in different grids. This report considers that it is possible to aim for and develop a standardized set of balancing instruments that is applicable for all regional hydrogen grids, in all diversities. Therefore, this is taken as a main requirement, despite that it might be that certain instruments are more or less important given certain situational characteristics and acknowledging that this set of instruments will develop further over time.

5.1 A set of balancing instruments for archetype 1-3 grids

Based on the balancing functions defined in phase 1, experiences in the electricity and gas sector and discussions with experts, a set of balancing instruments was identified (see Figure 3). This should not be interpreted as the one and only framework for balancing in archetype 1-3 grids, but as a starting point for future discussions between regulators, market parties and DSOs. The main insights from this assessment are the following.

Figure 3: Overview of potential balancing instruments in archetype 1-3 grids and linkages with the physical assets for balancing (chapter 4) and supportive instruments. Balancing instruments are defined as agreements and structured frameworks between the trading party(s), connected parties and DSO enabling to deploy flexibility options and technical aspects for the physical balancing of the grid.

Agreements in trading contracts are the primary instruments for balancing in archetypes 1-3

Trading parties are responsible for maintaining portfolio balance at all times. In archetypes 1 and 2 portfolio balancing is part of the commodity trading agreements in the trading contracts between the trading party and connected parties are structured, as there is just one trading party. Exchange and trade between portfolios is only possible from archetype 3 onwards, when multiple trading parties are present. As a result, portfolio balancing in archetypes 1 and 2 does is primarily arranged within bilateral trading contracts between the trading party and connected parties.

Rather than a single, uniform instrument, the trading contract can be seen as a toolbox of contractual balancing mechanisms and agreements to enable the trading party to manage its portfolio optimally. The options to do this are endless and trading parties are specialized in this. Therefore, the type of agreements in trading contracts will not be discussed in detail in this report and are left for these market parties. For the general reader, it should however be indicated that the trading contracts can include a large diversity of agreements, for example agreements related to 1) portfolio optimization and commodity trading (such as: volume, profile, firmness and prioritization agreements, etc.); 2) to short term portfolio balancing (such as: capacity limiting, capacity-steering, flexibility back-up and disturbance/outage response clauses, etc.); and 3) supporting clauses (such as: DSO interaction clauses, communication & expectation management clauses, explicit risk allocation clauses, etc.). The trading parties are expected to have a lot of freedom to custom these agreements with the connected parties in their portfolio.

Several balancing instruments are to be considered for system balancing actions

In reality it is considerable, even despite the portfolio balancing of market parties, that the pressure in the grid can drop or increase below or above the predefined thresholds for maintaining system integrity. The DSO will signal this via measurements in the grid. There are a few balancing instruments that can be considered to perform system balancing actions:

1. The DSO can contract flexibility from connected parties that can be activated when the system is not in balance (here referred to as ‘contracted flex’).

2. The DSO can utilize flexibility that is owned/managed by themselves, such as linepack and/or decentralized storage if regulatory allowed (here referred to as ‘DSO managed flex’).
3. The DSO can restrict connected parties or trading party(s) when non-firm agreements were made in the transport contracts (here referred to as ‘restrictions’).
4. Finally, the DSO can perform integrity actions, such as (partially) closing the valves, as a last resort in case of emergency (here referred to as ‘emergency actions’).

In archetype 3 distribution grids certain supportive instruments for portfolio balancing can be considered

When distribution grids involve multiple trading parties, and therefore are categorized as archetype 3, certain supportive instruments for portfolio balancing might be considered, such as:

- Nominations (in advanced or limited forms) by which the DSO is informed by the trading parties on the planned entry and exit volumes at specific locations at the grid;
- Imbalance signals provided by the DSO towards the trading parties if it turns out that the total of portfolio’s from the trading parties are not in balance. The trading parties can perform renominations to adjust their own portfolio’s in order to make the total of portfolio’s in balance;
- Transport capacity trading platform to provide the opportunity for trading parties to trade transport rights between them. Only adds value when there is sufficient liquidity in the market;
- Flexibility services to provide the opportunity for trading parties to offer unused flexibility within their portfolio to other trading parties that might be in need of it. Only adds value when there is sufficient liquidity in the market.

Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden. summarizes the potential set of balancing instruments and supportive instruments for archetypes 1-3 identified in this report. Despite the fact that other mechanisms and tools could be added or some could be arranged completely differently, this set of balancing instruments should be sufficient as one of the possible generic schemes to balance archetype 1-3 grids. In Appendix D, all the individual balancing instruments are explained on their key principles and implications in Archetype 1-3 grids.

Table 6: Summary of balancing instruments and supportive instruments highlighted in this report

Instrument	System /portfolio balancing	Timing (interval)	Parties (TP & CP)
Balancing instruments and supportive instruments	System /portfolio balancing	15 min >year	TP & CP

Flex contra ct	System balanci ng	Sec – wee k	DS O & CP				
DSO mana ged flexibi lity	System balanci ng	Sec – hou r	DS O				
Restri ctions (non- firm)	System balanci ng	Sec – day	DS O & TP /C P				
Integri ty action s	System balanci ng	Sec – min	DS O (& CP)				
Trans port contra ct	Support ive to system balanci ng	Yea r	DS O & TP				
Nomi nation s	Support ive to portfoli o balanci ng	Day - ahe ad	TP (& DS O)				
Imbal ance signal s & reno minati ons	Support ive to portfoli o balanci ng	5 min – hou rs	TP (& DS O)				
Trans port capaci ty tradin g platfo rm	Support ive to portfoli o balanci ng	Hou r – wee ks	TP				
Flexibi lity	Support ive to portfoli	15 min –	TP				

servic o hou
 es balanci rs
 ng

*DSO= Distribution System Operator, TP= Trading party(s), CP= Connected party(s).

**X= (likely) required, O= optional, empty= not relevant.

5.2 Requirements to design balancing enabling mechanisms

For the balancing instruments and supportive instruments described in previous chapter, requirements were identified that are needed to implement such an instrument successfully. An overview of the identified requirements per instrument is available upon request. In this chapter overarching insights are presented based on this inventory.

There is a set of requirement categories that were relevant for all balancing instruments

From the inventory of requirements of the example set of balancing instruments and supportive instruments, the following general insights should be considered for the design process of the archetype 1-3 balancing regime:

- The set and design of balancing instruments should be standardized and applicable for all regional hydrogen grids, despite their unique and situational characteristics;
- The design and requirements for balancing instruments are very interrelated;
- For instruments that are only valuable under certain circumstances (e.g. the capacity market trading platform and flexibility services) a consideration is to be made what to do with these types of instruments: 1) not include them, 2) activate them when specific conditions are met, or 3) include them in such a way that they at least cannot harm the system when they are not relevant (yet);
- Categories for general requirements for balancing instruments were identified (see Table 7);
- A point of attention is how to test if a designed structure of balancing instruments is sufficient and performing as designed.

Table 7: Overview of the identified general categories of requirements for designing the set of balancing instruments and its supportive instruments.

<p>Regulative and legislative</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety limits and requirements • Distinction of market rules, roles and responsibilities • Legal basis on when certain system balancing actions might be performed • Regulation of DSO related activities and mechanisms, such as flex contracts
<p>Technical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measuring the data required for decision making, activation and reconciliation • Required technical and physical limitations of assets and technologies
<p>Organizational and operational</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The required ‘back-office’ to operate and execute the instruments • Trained personnel and internal processes • Communication protocols to external parties
<p>Contractual</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contractual definitions relevant for the mechanisms, such as firmness levels, non-firm, interruptible Agreements on when are actions allowed and when not, prioritization and consequences Settlement rules, billing and penalties for causers and non-compliance to contractual agreements
<p>IT & data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interfaces for data collection, analysis, decision making/control and communication Automation of processes requires standardized, predefined processes that should be robust to apply on different hydrogen grids with unique characteristics
<p>Other</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interest of market parties to become a trading party on archetype 1-3 grids and/or to contribute to balancing instruments where trading parties or connected parties are involved Number of trading parties at grids might determine the liquidity and other relevant requirements. The structure of balancing instruments should be designed such that they support all possible situations

The assessment of requirements for balancing instruments shows no fundamental show-stoppers, but highlights several critical points of attention.

One of the purposes of assessing the requirements of this optional balancing framework was to explore if any significant issues or bottlenecks would arise for developing balancing regimes for archetype 1-3 distribution grids. Despite that some of the requirements are complex, challenging and/or time consuming, no show-stoppers were identified.

Based on the requirement analysis of the example set of balancing instruments, their requirements and the implications described above, an indicative evaluation is performed on the feasibility characteristics of these set of balancing instruments. These are summarized in Table 8.

Table 8. Indicative evaluation on the feasibility characteristics of the set of balancing instruments.

Feasibility characteristics	Evaluation	Remark
Regulatory & legal	Point of attention	New and existing regulation and legislation needs to be adapted and developed. This takes time and involves uncertainty.
Technical	No significant issues identified	Minimal technical requirements need to be in place and this can differ per grid. But no significant issues expected.
Organizational	Point of attention	Additional investigation on what ‘back-office’/ operational organisation for DSO and market parties should contain is relevant to get an indication of the costs involved.
Economic & cost	Uncertain	Unclear what costs the instruments involve and what volumes are required in a regional network to make them feasible and efficient.

Market & participation	Point of attention	Involving market parties in the design of the balancing regime is essential and deserves special attention.
IT infrastructure & data	No significant issues identified	Development of IT infrastructure can be complex and facing delays, but no significant issues identified.

6. Response times of balancing instruments

In the first phase of this project, an initial quantification of example networks has provided a first indication of the challenges involved in balancing regional hydrogen grids. The example calculations for typical networks show that required response times can be expected to be in the order of minutes. Calculations of DSO networks currently in development confirm this order of magnitude, with some projections showing even shorter response times.

The implications for the required functionalities of a balancing system, the required response times for deploying balancing tools as a consequence of the expected imbalance, and the (residual) risks and costs of imbalances across different time horizons remain unclear. The goal of this research activity is therefore to **assess the impact of estimated time scales on the balancing system design**. As the challenge is greatest in stand-alone networks, we focus on hydrogen grids in archetype 1-3.

6.1 Response time ranges

Since the availability of several important balancing tools can change significantly when the required response time is only a few minutes rather than several minutes, we define multiple response time ranges and assess the balancing system within each range. Response time is defined as the time required to react to an imbalance before grid system protection is activated. The response time ranges are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Response time ranges associated with balancing in regional hydrogen grids of archetype 1-3.

Range 1	Range 2	Range 3
1 hour to 15 minutes	15 minutes to 1 minute	1 minute to seconds

The third response time range is the most critical: having only seconds to one minute available significantly complicates the inclusion of human intervention and excludes the technical applicability of several flexibility options. Range 2 covers response times of up to 15 minutes. This upper bound was chosen because renominations and/or market clearing in hydrogen grids may follow the design of the electricity system, where a 15-minute interval is used for these balancing aspects⁶. Finally, response time range 1 covers periods from 15 minutes up to one hour, addressing the remaining response time requirements that are still considered critical.

Severity of balancing incidents is determined by linepack and relative supplier and offtake capacity

The balancing mechanism is classified into these three categories because the response times required for balancing the grid mainly depend on several key system characteristics:

1. **Available linepack.** The pipeline capacity represents the total usable pipeline volume, determined by the pipeline’s length and diameter. Subtracting the already occupied range due to the pressure drop required for gas transport, results in the available linepack.
2. **Supplier capacity.** The relative size and delivery capability of the supplier compared with the available pipeline capacity.
3. **Offtake capacity.** The relative size and demand of the offtake in relation to the available pipeline capacity.

⁶ There is little certainty about planned renomination and market clearing intervals set by Hynetwork. If these are to be hourly, it would be desirable to adhere to these at moment of coupling. Whether the time interval should then be per 15 minutes before system coupling is still up for debate.

For example:

- A network with a short total length (~ 1 km) and small diameter (~DN100) does not necessarily belong to range 3; it can also fall into range 1 or 2 if the connected party is also small in terms of the imbalance it causes.
- A network with a large pipe diameter (~DN400) can also be classified as range 1 or 2 if a connected party has very large demand or supply.

Because regional hydrogen grids are highly diverse and can involve many combinations of the factors described above, the signal chain and several chains of actions are analysed within the balancing system and their associated time scales, to draw conclusions about the feasibility and desirability of balancing tools within each response time range type. These chains include:

Chain of actions	Underlying functionalities
1. Monitoring: measurement and data processing	F5: Measurement and data management
2. Portfolio balancing via renominations	F3b: Match of feed-in and offtake with other trading parties F4b: Renomination based on review
3. Portfolio balancing outside renominations	F7b: Deliberate deviation from nominations to improve total system imbalance
4. System balancing actions	F8a: Deployment of flexibility services to maintain system integrity F8b: Gradual and incremental intervention F8c: Physical intervention based on projected system integrity loss

6.2 Balancing chains of actions and associated times

Balancing a hydrogen distribution grid is not a single action but a sequence of interconnected steps. Each step requires a certain amount of time, and the total duration of these steps determines whether the system can respond within a given response time range. Understanding these chains of actions and their associated time scales is therefore essential for assessing which balancing tools are technically feasible and operationally appropriate.

The measurement and data processing chain should be automated and limited to seconds

Monitoring forms the foundation of any balancing mechanism. Before corrective action can be taken, the system must first detect and confirm the presence of an (expected) imbalance. The monitoring requirements depend strongly on how quickly the system must detect and react to imbalance events. Short response times require highly automated, near real-time monitoring, whereas longer response times allow for more conventional data collection and validation processes.

Key elements of the monitoring chain include:

- **Frequency of measurement acquisition**
 Measurements may be continuous, high-frequency (e.g., second-by-second), or periodic (e.g., every few minutes)⁷. Faster response requirements generally necessitate higher measurement frequency to ensure that imbalances are detected promptly.
- **Data transmission delays**
 After measurement, sensor data must be transmitted to the control or monitoring system. Communication infrastructure (e.g., SCADA systems, telemetry networks) may introduce delays, particularly if data aggregation or buffering is involved.
- **Data validation and processing time**
 Incoming data must be checked for plausibility, filtered for noise, and processed to identify meaningful imbalance signals. This step can involve automated algorithms and, in some cases, manual validation, both of which add to the overall response time.
- **Decision-making and action initiation delays**
 Once an imbalance is detected, an alarm is generated and a decision must be made regarding the appropriate corrective action. Depending on the response time range, this may be fully automated or require human intervention. The time needed to trigger and initiate the corrective measure is a critical component of the total balancing time.

Together, these monitoring-related steps define the earliest point at which corrective action can realistically begin. Their combined duration therefore sets a lower bound on the achievable response time within the balancing system. This lower bound is applicable to response time range 3, where a delay of seconds can already be too much. In ranges 2 and 1, more slack can be given to sending signals and processing data. The resulting time scales are shown in Table 10.

Table 10. Minimum response times for measurements and data processing in different response time ranges for regional hydrogen grids of archetype 1-3.

Element	Range 1 (1 hour to 15 minutes)	Range 2 (15 minutes to 1 minute)	Range 3 (1 minute to seconds)
Measurement acquisition	Seconds	Seconds	Seconds
Data transmission	Seconds	Seconds	Seconds
Data validation and processing time	Seconds (preferably automatic)	Seconds (automatic)	Seconds (automatic)
Decision-making and action initiation delays	Seconds to minutes	Seconds (preferably automatic)	Seconds (automatic)

The first boundary condition for time scales is the measurement frequency, which in the case of pressure and flow measurements for balancing is likely to be in the range of seconds. In order to be able to respond to the most challenging imbalance situations, a grid needs to be prepared to respond quickly. This implies continuous measurement in many regional hydrogen grids, which comes with additional costs and raises operational risks related to the availability and reliability of measurement

⁷ To get a sense of the response and processing time of the measurements, it is important to note that multiple technologies are currently available for hydrogen flow measurement. The current focus is on Coriolis flow meters, which can achieve response times in the range of 50–200 ms. For pressure sensors, response times are typically in the range of approximately 5–50 ms, taking into account filtering, communication, and PLC processing.

infrastructure in systems that depend on near-continuous information. In grids where balancing response types are not critical (>1 hour), a 5-minute interval can for example be considered instead.

A next boundary condition is the data transmission: this is less of a design parameter and more so a delay that is present in nearly all monitoring chains. The technical limit is likely to be seconds at most. However, this assumes direct communication via cable, which will come with additional costs, as in the case of measurement frequency.

Finally, data validation and decision-making are mainly determined by the level of automation: validating data can in some cases be done manually in response time range 1, but considering the frequency this is not desirable. Decision-making and action initiation can be done manually in case the response time is in minutes to hours. However, in response time range 2 and likely also range 1, constant monitoring by dedicated staff can be costly.

In conclusion, the measurement and data processing chain should be limited to seconds in case the response time is within a minute, and can possibly be extended towards minute(s) for longer response time ranges 1 and 2 in case validation and processing is done manually. However, automation of the data chain seems preferable for most regional hydrogen grids. As a result, there is little variation in the resulting response times.

Portfolio balancing through renominations and market platform are constrained by predetermined time intervals

Balancing the grid through the adjustment of contracted feed-in and offtake volumes is the first chain of actions considered. This can be done via renominations and trading on a market platform, if available. However, renomination and market platforms are only expected to be present in grids of archetype 3 with a considerable amount of trading parties, and may not be present in grids in archetypes 1 and 2, and in earlier stages of development. Instead, nominations and renominations will likely take form in direct, bilateral communication between trading parties and the DSO.

In this approach, market participants modify their scheduled quantities in response to imbalance signals, thereby restoring balance at the portfolio level rather than through direct physical intervention by the BRP or, if portfolio balancing options are exhausted, by the system operator.

In the case that these (re)nominations happen through direct, bilateral communication, the availability depends on the agreements made beforehand, between trading parties and DSO. The parties may agree on a minimum lead time before delivery, after which positions can no longer formally be changed and must be communicated to the DSO. Given that human decision-making is likely required, a lead time of at least 15 minutes is considered appropriate.

In the case that these functionalities *are* present in a more advanced form such as a platform, their availability is dependent on the renomination time interval and the associated market clearing process. A key design choice for (regional) hydrogen grids concerns whether both balancing intervals should be set at 15 minutes (current electricity market) or one hour (current gas market). Adhering to the choice made on the national grid by Hynetwork is advisable as well.

Given that the response time ranges identified in this study fall within the scale of minutes, an hourly interval for both balancing intervals would significantly limit the effectiveness of portfolio balancing for short-term imbalances. An hourly interval may be too coarse to address rapidly developing system deviations, particularly in response time ranges of only seconds to 15 minutes.

A 15-minute interval aligns more closely with the operational realities of short-term balancing and is consistent with practices in electricity markets. While the final decision rests with policymakers and

market participants, a 15-minute clearing interval appears to be the most appropriate compromise between operational responsiveness and market feasibility. Increasing the frequency would add substantial administrative complexity for trading parties, with little additional benefit beyond solutions outside the renomination and market platform. For this analysis, we will assume the market clearing and renomination interval to be 15 minutes. Shorter intervals likely increase administrative burden and require more automated decision-making. However, for networks with low response times, such intervals may still be appropriate and should therefore be assessed on a case-by-case basis.

The relevant actions are described in the phase one report as functionality 3b: *Match of feed-in and offtake with other trading parties*, and functionality 4b: *Renomination based on review*.

Portfolio balancing outside renominations and market platform depend heavily on the flexibility of the asset used

In addition to (formal) renominations, portfolio balancing can also occur outside structured market intervals. In this case, connected parties adjust their feed-in or offtake in direct response to imbalance signals, *without renominating or informing the system operator*. These signals include a system imbalance signal or an individual portfolio imbalance signal (comparable to the SBS and POS signals for natural gas).

The motivation for changing the feed-in or offtake in this way is the projected consequences of imbalance. These consequences are the allocated costs of system balancing actions, or the effects of the closing of valves. Noticing they are in an imbalance position and that the system is in imbalance as well, they can prevent said consequences by adjusting their flow to return (as far as possible) to a balanced position.

This mechanism relies heavily on the technical flexibility of the connected assets. An *asset* here concerns the production or off-take installation, or a buffer or storage unit within the portfolio of a trading party. The ability to ramp production up or down, temporarily curtail demand, or activate flexible consumption processes determines how quickly and effectively the imbalance can be mitigated. Assets with fast ramping capabilities can contribute meaningfully even within shorter response time ranges, whereas less flexible installations may only be suitable for longer response intervals.

This action is described in the phase one report as functionality 7b: *Deliberate deviation from nominations to improve total system imbalance*.

System balancing actions as fallback options need to respond quickly

When portfolio-based measures are insufficient or too slow, the distribution system operator (DSO) may implement direct system balancing actions. These actions focus on maintaining system stability, preventing or solving imbalance when the market is unable to do so.

System balancing actions can include:

- **Modification of nomination through flexible contracts**

A first system balancing action is the modification of the nominated flow of a trading party by the DSO. If an imbalance is expected, or transport integrity in the system is not able to be facilitated, the DSO can choose to use this balancing action. It needs to be agreed upon at an earlier stage and be part of the contract structure, either through an interruptible or flexible contract. This action is described in the phase one report as functionality 4d: *Modification of trading party's nomination and/or impose restrictions to connected party*

- **Deployment of flexibility services by DSO**

If available, local hydrogen storage can be used to inject or withdraw from the system to temporarily compensate for supply-demand mismatches. Storage provides a buffering function and can be particularly valuable in short to medium response time ranges.

This action is described in the phase one report as functionality 8a: *Deployment of flexibility services to maintain system integrity.*

Both of the system balancing actions can and most likely need to have fast response times. However, it can be undesirable to use often, either because of higher costs (e.g. deployment of storage) or frequent and unexpected change of the operation at the connected party's asset.

System integrity actions as a last resort ensure safe operation of the network

Finally, system integrity actions should always be seen as a last resort. These actions include closing of valves that the DSO can use to ensure pressure remains within the safe zone of operation, and can have significant consequences for all connected parties on the network.

- **Gradual adjustment of connection-party valve throughput**

The DSO may reduce the physical flow at specific connection points to counteract developing imbalances. This is typically a controlled and progressive intervention.

This action is described in the phase one report as functionality 8b: *Gradual and incremental intervention.*

- **Instantaneous interventions (e.g., shut-off valves)**

In critical situations where system integrity is at risk, immediate protective actions may be required. These include rapid shut-off of flows to prevent pressure violations or other safety-related issues. Such measures are typically considered last-resort actions aimed at safeguarding the network.

This action is described in the phase one report as functionality 8c: *Physical intervention based on projected system integrity loss.*

System integrity actions need to have fast response times or be instantaneous, to ensure safe operation of the network. They come with significant costs and consequences and should be used only if all other options are exhausted. Here it becomes necessary to prioritize the different balancing actions.

Prioritizing balancing actions

Together, these portfolio-based and system-level actions form a layered balancing framework, with different tools becoming relevant depending on the required response time and the severity of the imbalance.

Learning from the Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF), which extends the current electricity market design in European markets, four distinct operating zones can be identified: green, yellow, orange, and red (as presented in **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**). This zonal approach can also be applied to define and distribute the roles and responsibilities between the trading party and the Distribution System Operator (DSO) in a regional hydrogen distribution grid. To give an indication of pressures that *could* be associated with these zones, indicative pressure zones are given.

- **Green zone:** in this zone, the grid is considered unconstrained. The trading party can utilize the network capacity without restrictions, as long as they are in balance. The DSO's role is limited to active monitoring of network pressure and ensuring that operations remain within secure technical limits. Indicative pressure: 10-14 bar

- **Yellow zone:** when there is imbalance and system pressure moves to yellow zone, the trading party needs to do a renomination so that it goes back to the green zone (functionalities 3b & 4b). In addition to renomination, the trading party may directly activate and control flexibility within its portfolio, including both suppliers and consumers, to mitigate the imbalance (functionality 7b). Indicative pressures: 9-10 and 14-15 bar.
- **Orange zone:** if the pressure continues to increase and enters the orange zone, and if sufficient market-based flexibility is unavailable, the DSO is permitted to temporarily overrule market outcomes to prevent further deterioration toward the red zone. This may involve the activation of decentralized storage facilities or gradual valve adjustments to stabilize the system (functionality 8a & 8b). Indicative pressures: 8-9 and 15-16 bar.
- **Red zone:** this is where DSO system protection takes place, the shut-off valve will be active to cut the connection (functionality 8c). Indicative pressures: <8 bar and >16 bar.

Figure 4. The USEF framework with four operating zones for electricity grids. Note: the role distribution mentioned here is not always applicable to hydrogen.

6.3 Impact of varying response times

The previous chapters have given an overview of minimum response times and what factors influence them, as well as a prioritization of actions inspired by the USEF. Here we will synthesize these topics and determine the flexibility needs for regional grids in different response time ranges.

In Table 11, an overview is given of the expected availability of the balancing actions described above. Here we assume a system that works with automated data collection and decision-making, with no human-in-the-loop.

Table 11. The expected availability of several balancing actions for different response time ranges of regional hydrogen networks. ‘Not used’ is used here for actions that are possible, but should not be used in all cases – in response time range 3 instantaneous interventions are still possible, but it is not desirable to ever use them, given the flexibility in the rest of the system.

Balancing action	Range 1 (1 hour to 15 minutes)	Range 2 (15 minutes to 1 minute)	Range 3 (1 minute to seconds)
Portfolio balancing via renominations and market platform	Possible		
Portfolio balancing outside nominations and market platform	Possible		
Modification of nomination through flexible contracts	Possible		
System balancing by deployment of flexibility services by DSO	Possible		
System integrity action	Range 1	Range 2	Range 3
Gradual adjustment of connected-party valve throughput	Not used		
Instantaneous interventions (e.g., shut-off valves)	Not used		

If an imbalance situation calls for a response time within 15 minutes, it is not possible to perform a portfolio balancing action via renomination or a market platform. This is under the assumption that the time intervals of both systems will be set at 15 minutes. If set at hourly, it will be unavailable for even response time range 1.

Secondly, the availability of portfolio balancing actions outside nominations and a market platform, are highly dependent on the technical flexibility of the asset. If the response time is less than a minute, the asset should be able to ramp up or down within seconds. It follows that in situations where the response time is in minutes, the flexibility of the asset should at least match that.

The deployment of flexibility service by DSO follows the same pattern. This functionality, likely performed by local storage, will only be present in case the market is unable to sufficiently balance the system. In general, system balancing actions should always be able to respond in seconds if the response time is equally short. However, these actions should be seen as a **last resort**. If a storage facility is present, it will then need to have the appropriate flexibility to respond within seconds. Still, the deployment should be automated, as having multiple parties involved with manual decision-making will slow the process down too much to be able to respond in time.

Finally, the gradual adjustment of valves and instantaneous interventions should be able to respond within seconds at any time. These are the fallback options and it is not desirable to use these as

balancing options unless all other options have been exhausted. Therefore they have been designated as 'not used' in response time range 1.

6.4 Conclusions on the impact of response time scales

The result of the analysis in this report further investigates the challenges of balancing a regional hydrogen grid, especially in archetypes 1-3. Previous calculations have shown that regional grids can face response times as low as under a minute, depending on the pipeline capacity and size of suppliers and off-takers in the system.

To evaluate the impact on the availability of balancing actions, three response time ranges have been defined: range 1 (1 hour to 15 minutes), range 2 (15 minutes to 1 minute) and range 3 (1 minute to seconds) for critical imbalance incidents. The evaluation shows that many balancing actions are not feasible, and much relies on the flexibility of the assets of connected parties or DSO.

A closer look at the chain of monitoring and data processing for balancing shows that **automation of decision-making is essential**. Many steps have a technical limit within seconds, not adding a lot of time to the total response time. The first of these steps, measurement frequency, is a design choice and is advised to set at second(s) intervals, in case the response time is lower than a minute.

Portfolio balancing actions are dependent on the renomination and market clearing intervals. Given the critical response times of ranges 2 and 3 (lower than 15 minutes), we advise to **set the renomination and market clearing intervals at 15 minutes**. This matches the intervals of the electricity markets. Furthermore, balancing actions through renominations or a market platform are already unavailable for response time ranges 2 and 3. If the interval were hourly, these functionalities would be unavailable for all critical response time ranges.

Portfolio balancing outside renominations and a market platform **heavily depend on the flexibility of the asset** in the portfolio. An asset here concerns the production or off-take installation, or a buffer or storage unit within the portfolio of a trading party. To be able to respond in seconds or minutes, the asset needs to be able to ramp up or down in a similar time. In addition, this assessment of portfolio balancing actions assumes automated decision-making, highlighting the importance of automation. If these processes are not automated, they are either unavailable to be used within a minute, or would require constant manual monitoring through some form of a control room. This is likely unattractive in regional hydrogen grids.

Finally, system balancing actions should always be able to respond in seconds if the response time is equally short. However, these actions should be seen as a **last resort**. Flexibility services can be deployed by the DSO, but costs will be allocated to causers of imbalance. Gradual or instantaneous closing of valves can severely impair operation of the rest of the system and is reserved for maintaining system integrity, rather than being available for balancing.

In conclusion, in response times below 15 minutes, which many regional grids are expected to face, **the balancing system relies heavily on the flexibility of assets for portfolio balancing and local storage**. This concerns the physical ramp up or ramp down speeds: the technical flexibility determining the response time. These assets have to be able to respond in seconds or minutes, before intervention through (gradual) shut-down of the system takes place.

Part II

From Regional to National Integration

7. System coupling of DSO and TSO: three balancing approaches

System coupling of DSO and TSO networks

In Archetypes 4 and 5, the regional hydrogen grid connects to the national grid (HNS) via a physical system coupling, enabling unidirectional (Archetype 4) or bidirectional (Archetype 5) flows. Since the HNS operates at higher pressures, this requires pressure-reducing stations, compressors, and potentially purification stages (such as a PSA) if the Dutch government (KGG) allows for varying purity standards between the national and regional systems; hydrogen can flow from pure to impure without issues, but flowing from impure to pure requires active purification. A strict safety regime must be established collaboratively by the DSO and TSO, covering pressure protection, flow monitoring, and emergency shut-offs. To prevent redundant investments, decisions on if, where, and when a system coupling is made must be defined early.

More importantly, a connection to the national network expands the balancing capabilities of distribution grids. Flexibility throughout the connected system can be used for balancing the regional grid, provided technical and operational systems are aligned.

In all three coordination approaches described in this chapter, the entry-exit structure differs. In the pressure-controlled and central portfolio approaches, a single shared entry-exit system applies to the combined network. In the separate portfolio approach, two distinct entry-exit systems operate in parallel, one per grid operator. This separation adds operational complexity but preserves the independence of each balancing regime.

Three approaches for portfolio balancing after system coupling

Three plausible options for coordination approaches emerge when coupling regional and national hydrogen networks: (1) pressure-controlled, (2) separate portfolio balancing, and (3) central portfolio balancing.

Figure 5. Schematic overview of the three possible portfolio balancing regimes for archetypes 4 and 5.

Pressure-controlled balancing regime

The first and most simple balancing regime consists of balancing via a pressure setpoint on the connection point. This allows the regional grid to passively follow the pressure setpoint at the connection point. The national grid effectively absorbs the regional grid's balancing effort through this setpoint. This is how regional natural gas grids are currently balanced. Under this model, the TSO, or the BRP active at the connection point on the national side, absorbs the regional grid's portfolio imbalance within the national system.

As this balancing regime makes control at the level of individual connected parties impossible, it is only suitable for grids with predominantly unilateral flows from central supply to decentral demand. Additionally, the amount of local production needs to be small relative to the total network volume, as too much local production can cause pressure swings, which would make it difficult to operate at the connection point. This approach is cost-effective, but only works reliably when there is a consistent upstream flow sufficient to meet all downstream demand. It is not suitable for distribution grids with multiple producers or variable feed-in profiles. Pressure-controlled balancing on a connection point severely limits the involvement of a DSO in balancing.

Separate portfolio balancing regime

The second option is to operate separate portfolio balancing regimes for the regional and national grid in parallel. The connection point is flow-controlled here, allowing more local production or even structural overproduction in the regional grid towards the national grid. It becomes an exchange point for two systems, rather than a simple entry/exit point in a central system.

Rather than comparing this connection point to an interconnection point between two countries, it is more accurate to view it as analogous to a green gas booster, a connection point where a smaller production system injects into a larger transmission network. The interconnection analogy incorrectly implies that instruments like Operational Balancing Agreements (OBAs) and Swaps are applicable here. OBAs are typically used for large transport volumes between Neighbouring Network Operators (such as TSOs, terminals and storage facilities), to administratively reconcile differences between physical flows and confirmed nominations without affecting shipper allocations; they are not appropriate for the limited commodity volumes expected on a regional hydrogen network. Swaps require a physical volume shift of gas between locations, which implies that at least two physical connections to the regional hydrogen network would be needed, which is not a typical infrastructure arrangement in this context. Furthermore, an interconnection analogy implies that shippers/BRPs on both sides must actively match positions, as is customary at cross-border points. This would mean shippers/BRPs active on the regional network would need to hold an entry and exit on the HNS and maintain a separate portfolio with HNS, which would add administrative complexity for what are relatively small commodity volumes. For these reasons, the green gas booster analogy better represents the functional scale and scope of this connection.

In the case of a regional grid that has already set up a portfolio balancing regime before the moment of coupling, keeping this system in place can be desirable. Having a system with more complex flows and a large amount of trading parties, can further substantiate the choice for separate regimes.

Central portfolio balancing regime

A third option is to have a single, central portfolio balancing regime encompassing both distribution and national grids. Nominations need to be submitted to a central market operator, and a central total portfolio imbalance signal is presented. Deviations from individual imbalances can then cause costs allocated by the central market operator. The connection point is flow-controlled in this case as well. Under this regime, each system operator (DSO and TSO) continues to manage system balancing on their own network independently. Only the portfolio balancing layer is operated centrally.

With more parties being connected to each other through this balancing system, more balancing options open up to all parties. This adds more accessible flexibility, facilitating balancing. Additionally, a central portfolio balancing regime adds clarity and can be easier to understand for parties involved

in both grids. Maintaining a single system also is likely to be more cost-efficient to maintain, with operational costs of separate systems expected to be higher.

However, the evolution through archetypes needs to be taken into account for this decision. If a balancing regime has been constructed for a regional network in earlier archetypes, this is made redundant when moving to a central balancing regime. This includes data-infrastructure, transport capacity booking, human capital and earlier investments in designing the balancing regime.

Selecting the balancing regime

The decision on which regime to opt for involves multiple considerations. The first consideration is to what degree the decision should be future-proof. This is a main drawback of the pressure-controlled balancing regime: it is a relatively simple and cost-effective regime as long as there is limited feed-in in the distribution grid. However, this regime might not be sufficient if feed-in would increase beyond certain levels. Both the separate and centralized regimes can be considered robust for changes.

The second consideration is whether all regional grids should have the similar type of regime, or whether a decision for a regime can be made per regional grid. The advantage of the former is standardization a level of playing field between regions. The advantage of the latter is that more customized decisions per region can be made.

In the latter case the approaches are not mutually exclusive. A newly established regional grid may opt for pressure-controlled balancing or join a central portfolio platform, while an existing grid with a functioning separate regime may retain it. Regimes 2 and 3 can therefore coexist across different regional networks simultaneously.

Based on current insights from grid operators and the considerations above, the separate regime is currently considered the most realistic and viable path for most regional grids. It minimises overhead and administrative burden while accommodating local complexity and structural overproduction. The central portfolio regime remains a viable long-term option and may be the optimal choice for grids that are newly established and lack prior balancing infrastructure. It should be noted that significant uncertainties remain, and this assessment may evolve as the hydrogen market matures.

8. Considerations for system coupling

Coupling regional to national networks creates a robust system in which each individual coupling must demonstrate the necessity and a positive societal business case based on several case-specific factors.

System coupling costs

A bidirectional system coupling requires substantially higher investments due to costs of a booster. While operational costs are covered via transport fees, allocating investment costs depends on governmental policy. Options range from broad socialization to a strict 'user-pays' model. Because a system coupling primarily facilitates structural commercial trade rather than just imbalance resolution, allocating costs based on traded volumes is a highly viable option.

For unidirectional or passively breathing grids, regional users clearly benefit, making 'user-pays' logical, with costs being socialized through the transport costs over the system coupling. However, bidirectional couplings benefit both regional and national trading parties. To avoid penalizing regional 'early adopters' with exorbitant tariffs for infrastructure yielding national value, cost allocation must reflect this dual benefit, clearly distinguishing between structural commercial trading and incidental system balancing.

A valid alternative, under the Energy Act's principle that network costs should be minimised, is to connect early adopters who cannot achieve local balance directly to the TSO rather than requiring costly bidirectional infrastructure at the DSO level. This avoids the situation where early regional projects must bear the cost of bidirectional stations that primarily serve national-scale flows.

Quality of hydrogen

The KGG (Ministry of Climate Policy and Green Growth) sets the gas specifications for both the TSO and DSO networks and must explicitly allow for differences in purity standards between them. Differences in hydrogen purity standards between national and regional grids strongly influence the coupling decision. Hydrogen of a higher purity can generally be used in grids where a lower purity standard is applied, but the other way round entails costly purification processes. Aligning with national standards versus absorbing purification costs must be evaluated per grid, considering prior HyDelta insights on societal optimums and strategies.⁸

Flexibility and competition

Coupling changes the financial landscape for connected parties: where local hydrogen pricing may previously have followed a stable reference price, a coupled system exposes buyers and sellers to national market dynamics and potentially greater price volatility. While the national network offers flexibility primarily via linepack (pipeline capacity), this does not automatically guarantee that all local imbalances are instantly or affordably resolved. Minor imbalances might still be managed more cost-efficiently within the regional network itself.

Furthermore, national integration increases competition, including with other local energy vectors such as heat, green gas, and electricity. This expanded market can lower off-taker costs but may diminish the business case for local flexibility providers. Ultimately, the coupling's added societal value must demonstrably outweigh its investments.

Conclusion on the system coupling decision

The coupling decision lies with the TSO and DSO, though early inclusion of trading and connected parties is vital to mitigate local market uncertainty. Key factors shaping this societal business case include: (1) DSO and TSO's strategic visions, (2) investment and cost allocation, (3) hydrogen quality alignment, (4) flexibility and competition, and (5) broader societal value by enabling market development, system integration, and increased market liquidity. Given the rapid development of Dutch grids, the projected coupling timeline heavily influences these outcomes. Regarding operations: given the high operating pressures of the HNS (above 16 bar), the physical coupling can in practice only be operated by the TSO.

Operation of a system coupling

Within the discussion on coupled networks, it is essential to strictly separate 'security of supply' from 'transport security'. Security of supply (the availability of hydrogen molecules) is primarily a market and Balance Responsible Party (BRP) task. Conversely, transport security revolves exclusively around the grid operator's task: continuously guaranteeing safe system pressure and network availability.

In early archetypes, safeguarding pressure relies entirely on local infeed and offtake. After a system coupling, the ultimate responsibility for transport security remains strictly with the respective grid owners (the DSO and TSO). In the pressure-controlled model, the connection point is governed by a

⁸ See previous HyDelta 3 work [D1a.1](#) and [D1a.2](#) and follow-up HyDelta 4 work [D3a.1](#) and [D3a.2](#) on gas quality.

pressure setpoint, but the DSO still actively manages the gas entering its regional grid based on commercial agreements and ensures pressure reduction stations function properly.

While a system coupling is operationally comparable to a regular large connection point, it is a strict requirement that the safety systems of the regional and national operators communicate seamlessly, particularly regarding emergency protocols and system balancing actions. Regardless of the chosen balancing regime, the technical configuration must always allow operators to monitor pressures and safely shut off entry points during extreme pressure events.

Buffer vessels and decentralized storage

In the uncoupled archetypes (1 to 3), the DSO and connected parties face the decision of whether to invest in decentralized storage. Small-scale storage can efficiently accommodate short-term local imbalances. The business case for connected parties heavily relies on dynamic pricing; if local hydrogen prices fluctuate, storage is highly lucrative. A distinction should be made between market-side storage (used for dynamic pricing and trading, which can also support system balancing) and DSO storage (used exclusively for system balancing and not for commercial trading). Users might also install behind-the-meter storage for profile flexibility, reducing network capacity booking costs or to buy time to safely ramp down production during emergency shut-offs. However, large-scale DSO buffering is generally not feasible pending the system coupling.

Once connected to the national grid, additional flexibility becomes available. While local storage faces more competition from large scale storage sites, there might still be value particularly for decentralized storage. The specific balancing regime choice does not completely dictate the utility of storage. Whether operating under a central platform or separate regimes, regional storage retains value for resolving short-term local imbalances and can participate in broader national trading. Because national flexibility (e.g., HyStock) does not guarantee an immediate, affordable solution for every local imbalance, regional storage remains highly relevant. Therefore, trying to prevent inefficient investments may result in local storage being sized conservatively initially, and DSOs must provide timely clarity regarding the national connection timeline to prevent unnecessary investments.

Contracts for system balancing

When working towards a system coupling, the distinction between commercial portfolio balancing and system balancing must remain clear. While a central portfolio system can efficiently handle market portfolio balancing, all network-related activities and contracts (including transport agreements, transport capacity products, physical connections, and specific system balancing actions) firmly remain with the respective grid operator.

This ensures the DSO can recover network costs through transport tariffs. However, a system coupling means trading parties on the distribution network could cause imbalances that require TSO balancing services. The allocation of these costs must be covered in agreements between the TSO and trading parties, or passed from the TSO to the DSO. All grid users must be informed of these allocation mechanisms prior to coupling.

Access for trading and connected parties

Because this project entails public networks, an obligation to connect generally applies across all archetypes, while transport itself is governed by contracted capacity rather than an unconditional obligation. Under the (upcoming) Energy Act, access can only be denied if there is an absolute lack of capacity and grid expansion is economically unjustifiable (unless the requesting party is willing to fund the expansion).

However, a strict distinction exists between a physical connection and a commercial transport contract. BRPs must ensure that their connected parties' projected flows fit within contracted capacities. Because this involves private agreements, a BRP is free to refuse a commercial contract if a connected party's highly demanding profile cannot be balanced within their portfolio.

As regional grids mature, capacity allocation may evolve to resemble the natural gas grid, utilizing multi-case simulations, capacity auctions, and open seasons for long-term entry/exit capacity. Until strict access regulations take full effect around 2033, policymakers, TSOs, and DSOs must collaboratively establish manageable frameworks for scarcity.

Market and price mechanisms

Beyond the choice of balancing regime, the market platform and price mechanisms must be addressed. A single, centrally operated market platform encompassing both transmission and distribution networks is highly advisable. It offers greater market liquidity, efficiency, and clarity for parties operating across both networks, even if the underlying balancing responsibilities remain separated. Multiple regional subsystems could potentially be linked into this central market platform.

Similarly, unified price mechanisms for balancing are essential. A single system of financial incentives prevents market manipulation and avoids contradictory incentives appearing side-by-side on a coupled grid.

Data and monitoring

The responsibility for operational measurements always lies with the respective grid operator. While a purely pressure-steered regional grid might technically require less active data exchange, managing real-world scarcity realistically demands structural flow-control. Therefore, moving toward central or actively communicating separate regimes necessitates robust, standardized data sharing. Only when transitioning to a fully integrated national portfolio platform will fundamentally new legal agreements regarding commercial data sharing be required between the DSO and TSO.

Intermediate conclusions

To conclude, three main portfolio balancing regimes exist when connecting a regional hydrogen network to the national grid via a system coupling: pressure-controlled balancing, a central portfolio balancing regime, and separate portfolio balancing regimes. Importantly, these regimes can operate in parallel across different regional networks, tailored to specific local circumstances. Pressure-controlled balancing suits unidirectional connections with minimal local production. A central regime simplifies market portfolio activities and lowers operational costs, while separate regimes accommodate grids with pre-existing complex setups. Ultimately, the chosen regime primarily dictates coordination methods, rather than limiting the physical viability of flexibility assets like decentralized storage.

The decision to couple involves assessing investment costs, hydrogen quality, flexibility, and competition. Crucially, a system coupling primarily facilitates broader commercial trade, not just imbalance resolution. Therefore, allocating coupling costs based on traded volumes is a highly viable option. Furthermore, realizing a physical coupling does not automatically guarantee that all local imbalances can be instantly resolved. Providing timely clarity and transparency on these coupling decisions remains the responsibility of the TSO and DSO, which is essential to secure investments and drive hydrogen market development.

While safety measures and coupling operations require case-by-case alignment between the DSO and TSO, other operational aspects are clear. While a central system is highly efficient for commercial market portfolio activities, all physical network-related activities and contracts firmly remain with the

respective grid operator (DSO). Data and monitoring responsibilities align similarly; even with separate regimes, IT infrastructures must communicate seamlessly. Finally, establishing a centrally operated market platform and unified price mechanisms is universally desirable to ensure market efficiency across the entire coupled hydrogen network.

Part III

Key Findings and Way Forward

9. Conclusions

Taken together, the preceding chapters work towards a harmonised balancing design for all hydrogen distribution grids, while leaving room for grid-specific differences. Across market needs, technical options, instrument design, and response-time requirements, a consistent picture emerges: early-stage grids will rely heavily on the availability of flexibility in connected assets and contractual arrangements in portfolio balancing, while Distribution System Operators must be prepared to safeguard system integrity through monitoring and well-defined escalation measures.

Initially, DSOs will have limited capabilities to solve imbalance situations; instead, the portfolio balancing through changes in feed-in and offtake of connected parties will need to be flexible enough to feasibly keep the grid in balance. To that end, trading parties need to assemble balanced portfolios and secure flexibility via (bilateral) contracts and operational agreements with connected assets. In practice, this means that balancing performance in the near term will depend less on centrally designed market mechanisms and more on whether trading parties can put workable portfolios in place and actively manage them as conditions change.

For trading parties and the market, a lot of freedom is left on how to arrange balancing in hydrogen distribution grids. On the other hand, this comes with a lot of uncertainty: how will the hydrogen sector develop? Will it become commercially interesting to start trading on hydrogen distribution grids? And how will the regulatory landscape develop? Therefore, it is important that market parties, DSOs and regulators build and keep close interactions to develop the initiatives into mature hydrogen distribution grids. This report has identified the playing field, vocabulary and frameworks to start these discussions.

In the longer term, once regional distribution grids are physically coupled to the national hydrogen system, balancing can likely draw on a wider pool of flexibility (e.g., larger linepack and, over time, central storage and more liquid trading), reducing reliance on purely local measures. This is a reason to make key design choices now, especially on standardisation, data exchange, roles, and interfaces, so early regimes can scale and connect without major redesign. At the same time, for many projects this coupled end-state is still some distance away, meaning local portfolio balancing and bilateral arrangements will remain the practical reality for the coming years.

Grid developments and market needs

When initiatives move towards open-access grids, a more structured and unified approach for hydrogen distribution grid balancing needs to be developed

An analysis of the first hydrogen grid developments and market needs underscores the urgency of jointly resolving balancing arrangements in ongoing grid projects. Whereas most projects currently are at a stage where balancing is (intended to be) solved solely via bilateral agreements, taking the next step in their development will require a collaborative approach to balancing. In projects that do consist of more connected parties and have a trading party actively taking up the role of BRP, discussions on the next phase of balancing are much more detailed. This report provides insights into those next steps.

A closer look at existing initiatives reveals that there are significant flexibility needs, covered by a diversity of flexibility options. The flexibility needs of future open-access distribution grids will depend on the combination of the parties connected. Preparation of market parties by matching supply- and demand-side flexibility for effective portfolio balancing is crucial. The design of a system balancing regime by the DSO needs to be able to maintain system integrity, but has a limited role in the daily balancing.

Market flexibility options and technical options for the DSO

Market participants are expected to balance their own portfolios by securing and aligning flexibility options and needs on both the entry and exit sides. When despite portfolio balancing, the system pressure exceeds predefined limits, the DSO has some technical options to intervene.

Considering flexibility options in stand-alone hydrogen grids reveals that options exist on both entry and exit sides. Trading parties face the challenge of attracting a suitable portfolio of these options, with sufficient low-cost flexibility providers. Flexibility options on entry side are especially found in SMR, gasification, hydrogen carrier reconversion and storage assets. Flexibility options on exit side are mostly found in assets not directly impacting primary, non-energy related, processes of the consumer, like hybrid boilers for example.

Only when market-based portfolio balancing is insufficient or too slow, the DSO may step in through an escalation mechanism aimed at preventing pressures from leaving safe operating limits. The available measures include deployment of flexibility services (e.g. hydrogen storage), incremental flow limitation at connection points and—where contractually agreed—utilising flexibility at connected parties.

Balancing instruments

The way in which market flexibility options and technical aspects of the DSOs can be structurally deployed for portfolio and system balancing is determined by the designed set of balancing instruments.

An analysis of balancing instruments shows that trading contracts are the primary instrument for portfolio balancing in archetypes 1-3. With the addition of multiple trading parties, more (supportive) portfolio balancing instruments may be considered. The DSO can manage system balance through a hierarchy of measures, starting with contractual and flexibility-based instruments and escalating, if necessary, to restrictive or physical integrity actions.

The assessment of requirements for balancing instruments shows no fundamental show-stoppers, but highlights several critical points of attention. First, it should be acknowledged that balancing instruments require new or updated regulation and legislation, which requires time and involves uncertainty. Secondly, it is yet still unclear what the organisational requirements are for DSO and market participants, including how the costs compare with the volumes of these grids. Thirdly, the involvement and (potential) commercial viability of market participants to participate in hydrogen distribution grids and the balancing regime.

Response times of balancing instruments

Given the second-minute response times required in hydrogen distribution grids, automation of decision making, digitization of assets and predefined processes are needed.

Considering response times in hydrogen grid balancing can be as short as seconds to a minute, automation of decision-making is essential. Additionally, portfolio balancing actions through communication with the network operator are only available if response times are longer (>15 minutes). Portfolio balancing without this communication (within a trading party's own portfolio) heavily depend on the flexibility of the asset in the portfolio. This may be required on the scale of seconds or minutes.

Finally, system balancing actions should always be able to respond in seconds if the response time is equally short. However, these actions should be seen as a last resort. As it is expected that system

balancing actions are limited in early grids in archetypes 1-3, this means that the balancing system relies heavily on the flexibility of assets for portfolio balancing and local storage.

Three options to couple the balancing regimes of national and distribution hydrogen grids

Based on today's knowledge, initially a separate balancing regime is preferred followed by development towards a centralized balancing regime for national and distribution hydrogen grids.

Coupling regional hydrogen grids to the national hydrogen system alters both market coordination and operational balancing dynamics. Three portfolio balancing regimes can be considered, when coupling national and regional grids: pressure controlled, separate portfolio balancing, and central portfolio balancing. A pressure-controlled regime is the least future proof, as this regime becomes insufficient if significant feed-in connects to the regional grid.

Another consideration is whether all regional grids opt for the same regime or that the regime is decided per regional grid. A central portfolio balancing regime offers the highest level of market liquidity, transparency, and long-term robustness. However, as separate distribution grid balancing systems might be developed and in place before system coupling, and due to high coordination requirements of a centralized system from the start, based on today's knowledge it is preferred and perceived as most practical to start with separate balancing regimes. This should be done without undermining the option to develop towards a centralized regime at a later point in time. Nevertheless, the analysis indicates that early strategic decisions on coupling and the portfolio balancing regimes are critical, as they influence future flexibility options, cost allocation, and market development trajectories across the hydrogen value chain.

Considerations for system coupling

A system coupling is not merely a technical connection, but a strategic design choice with far-reaching implications for investment decisions, market functioning, and operational responsibilities.

Coupling can significantly enhance flexibility and competition by granting access to national-scale resources, yet it does not eliminate the need for local balancing capabilities or clearly defined responsibilities between DSOs, TSOs, and market parties. Key factors such as cost allocation, hydrogen quality alignment, contract design, and data exchange must be addressed explicitly to avoid uncertainty and misaligned incentives. Importantly, system coupling should primarily be regarded as an enabler of structural commercial trade rather than a guaranteed solution for local imbalance resolution. Transparent decision-making, early stakeholder involvement, and clarity on the intended end-state are therefore essential to ensure that system coupling contributes positively to both regional grid development and the wider hydrogen market.

10. Remaining knowledge gaps and challenges

This report has explored the key considerations towards developing hydrogen distribution grid balancing regimes. Despite the extensive analysis presented in this report, hydrogen distribution grid balancing is in its early, immature stages. Still, this report identified the playing field, vocabulary and frameworks to start interaction between market parties, DSOs and regulators on this matter.

However, it should be recognised that there is a lot uncertain or unclear related to hydrogen distribution grid balancing. We distinguish four different categories: 1) short term research needs, 2) knowledge gaps that should be tackled during the proceeding development of projects/initiatives, 3) fundamental uncertainties that should be taken into account, and 4) general challenges.

Short-term research needs

- Detailed assessment of the required organisational aspects of balancing instruments and the economic implications, including expected operational costs, transaction costs, and minimum market sizes/transport volumes required to make certain instruments viable.

Knowledge gaps for projects developing

- Regulatory boundaries for DSO flexibility procurement, including under which conditions DSOs may contract, own, or operate flexibility and storage assets without distorting markets.
- Vision and perspective of the TSO and DSO on the end-goal hydrogen balancing regime of the future.

Fundamental uncertainties

- Uncertainties related to the speed and size of the hydrogen market development
- The timeline of distribution grids moving from bilateral agreements towards a more liquid market, including daily trading on hydrogen distribution grids.
- Uncertainties related to the regulatory developments related to hydrogen distribution grid balancing, for example the regulations related to hydrogen DSOs.

General challenges

- Developing practical governance models for system coupling, covering cost- and risk-sharing between TSOs, DSOs, and trading parties during both normal operation and emergency situations.
- Market behaviour and willingness to participate in balancing, including the commercial viability of trading parties to participate in regional hydrogen networks and connected parties on non-firm arrangements.

11. Recommendations per party

This chapter provides recommendations on what different types of stakeholders should do at this point in time, given that hydrogen distribution grid balancing is currently in its infancy stage and given the ambition to realise the first open access hydrogen distribution networks in the coming decade.

11.1 Recommendations for policymakers, market participants and DSO

First of all, given the challenges and uncertainties, collaboration and interaction between the different categories of stakeholders is essential:

- Bring all participants together in a regional hydrogen grid at an early stage to jointly discuss balancing, using this explorative research as talking points. Which party can deliver flexibility for balancing purposes? Are all parties aware of the integrity actions taken in case portfolio balancing is insufficient? And what is the most cost-effective way to prevent system balancing actions to be taken?
- Encourage each other to think one step further than the existing initiatives taking place. Acknowledge that balancing is a challenge that is relevant to collaborate on. Identify together situations and events that can take place and identify what exactly is needed from balancing instruments.
- Set up a design process with the initial initiatives towards a standardized and robust balancing regime for future hydrogen distribution grids in the Netherlands. Determine when steps need to be implemented.

11.2 Recommendations for policymakers

For policymakers and regulators it is important to be aware of the developments in decentral hydrogen initiatives and the likely balancing requirements in the future. As development and adaptations in regulation take time, it is important to identify the regulation needs for these grids. In this report the following were identified:

- Develop guidance on cost allocation principles for system coupling investments, ensuring that early regional adopters are not disproportionately burdened for infrastructure that provides national societal value.
- Provide clarity on long-term prospects of system coupling of national and regional grids throughout the Netherlands. If there is a societal business case to do so, clarity on the decision helps secure investments in regional grids.
- Identify the regulative and legislative requirements of the potential set of balancing instruments needed and develop a timeline for the development of legislation.
- Provide formal clarity on the degree and conditions in which it will be possible for DSOs to operate (gaseous) hydrogen storage facilities.
- Be aware that behaviour of electrolysis heavily depends on subsidy designs and characteristics. Therefore, they may impact the degree in which the short ramp up and down abilities of electrolyzers can be utilized for hydrogen distribution grid balancing.

11.3 Recommendations for trading parties and connected parties

For trading parties and connected parties, balancing will be preconditional for use of their grid connection. The role of one or multiple trading party(s) is essential to assign the portfolio balancing responsibility. There is uncertainty to what degree it is commercially interesting and viable to become a trading party on a hydrogen distribution grid in this point in time. However, it is clear that these are required to start and develop hydrogen distribution grids. Therefore, an active and entrepreneurial attitude will be required from market participants participating and developing these decentral initiatives into distribution grids. Which implies that these market participants:

- Actively contribute early in balancing design discussions, as contractual arrangements with connected parties will remain the primary source of flexibility in archetype 1-3 grids.
- Structure contractual agreements explicitly around firmness, response times, and imbalance consequences, reducing reliance on emergency system actions that may carry higher costs or operational risks.
- Develop balanced portfolios, combining variable and flexible assets (e.g. electrolysis, hybrid offtake, storage) to manage imbalance risks cost-effectively. Selection of the right connected parties to accept into the portfolio is crucial: combinations of flexible off-take with inflexible production and the other way round, or aiming for constant offtake profiles in absence of storage units.
- Be more aware of own production and consumption patterns, including short term fluctuations, than relatively small/medium scale connected parties used to be in natural gas grids.
- Consider to invest in automation and fast-responding assets, especially if operating in grids where response times fall below 15 minutes.
- When considering investments in flexible assets, look towards the future and possibly construct agreements on how this flexibility can be used for all balancing purposes on the grid.

- Anticipate changing market roles as system coupling approaches, including potential shifts towards national pricing, increased competition, and new allocation mechanisms for balancing costs.

11.4 Recommendations for the distribution system operator (DSO)

In hydrogen distribution grids balancing will likely significantly differ for the DSOs compared to natural gas. In natural gas distribution grids system balancing is arranged mechanically, breathing along with the balancing regime from the TSO. Archetype 1-3 hydrogen distribution grids will involve a decentral market and separate portfolio balancing regime. The role of the DSO is to maintain grid integrity and system balance, involving flow-based control and digitized and automated assets and operation. Moreover, this has consequences when system coupling with national networks is considered in future stages. Therefore, the DSO is recommended to:

- Design balancing regimes that are robust yet scalable, starting from simple and most essential measures in consultation with market participants and regulators towards system coupling with separate regimes and eventually even a central market integration with national regimes.
- Explicitly define escalation hierarchies for imbalance resolution, clearly distinguishing portfolio balancing actions, and when certain system balancing actions are required.
- Actively inform connected parties of their balancing obligations and help them either gain sufficient understanding of the balancing framework or explore options to participate via a trading party's portfolio.
- Use technical tools cautiously and predictably, such as incremental valves and storage, with clear contractual frameworks to avoid undermining market-based balancing incentives and to overcome safety issues.
- Prioritize system transparency and automation, particularly in monitoring, measurement, and signal generation, as response times in regional grids can be as short as seconds.
- Be aware that increasing digitization and automation needs raise the importance of privacy and IT-security for hydrogen grids.
- Provide timely clarity on system coupling plans, enabling market parties to make informed decisions about investments in local flexibility or storage.
- Align between DSO and TSO on national and regional balancing frameworks to avoid incompatible market designs when future system coupling occurs, especially regarding balancing intervals, price formation and data standards.

11.5 Next steps

To move balancing of regional hydrogen grids to the next stage, a coordinated and collective approach is required. The key next step is the development of a shared roadmap for balancing, in which DSOs, the TSO, market parties, and policymakers jointly define the pathway towards a more standardised, scalable, and integrated balancing framework. Such a roadmap should clarify roles and responsibilities, identify milestones for standardisation and system integration, and provide guidance on how to transition from project-based solutions to a more structured system. Active participation of all relevant stakeholders is essential: market parties are encouraged to engage in and contribute to the development of this shared roadmap, while policymakers are called upon to support and actively take part in this process. Establishing this joint direction will help reduce uncertainty, align expectations, and enable timely investments, thereby creating the conditions for a well-functioning and scalable hydrogen balancing framework.

References

- [1] S. Blom, R. Octaviano and N. Dooley, “D4a.1 Grid balancing development for hydrogen distribution grids: characteristics and key gaps,” HyDelta 4, 2025.
- [2] F. Uleman, S. Hers and R. d. Kler, “Verkenning van vraagrespons in de Nederlandse energie-intensieve industrie,” TNO, 2026.
- [3] V. M. Lopez, H. Ziar, J. Haverkort, M. Zeman and O. Isabella, “Dynamic operation of water electrolyzers: A review for applications in photovoltaic systems integration,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 182, 2023.
- [4] C. Wang, Y. Wei and L. Gao, “A flexible hydrogen-electricity coproduction system through the decoupling of units with different dynamic characteristics,” *Carbon Neutrality*, vol. 2, 2023.
- [5] K. d. Meijere and V. Suriya, “D3b.1 – Factsheet Ammonia Cracking Technologies,” HyDelta 3, 2024.
- [6] Y. Li, C. Luo and Q. Su, “Cold start-up study of methanol reformer based on chemical-looping combustion,” *Fuel*, vol. 317, 2022.
- [7] R. v. Zoelen, S. Mahfoozi, N. Dooley and D. Boer, “D2a.2 - Societal optimal hydrogen distribution,” HyDelta 3, 2024.

Appendices

A. Indicative flexibility needs based on potential entry and exit customers

The customers are divided into entry and exit customers, however, it should be noted that prosumers can exist, for example industrial plants that consume and produce hydrogen themselves and are able to extract or inject hydrogen into the grid.

Table 12 provides an overview of the key flexibility need characteristics from entry customers. These characteristics are:

1) An estimated likelihood of their existence in hydrogen distribution grids.

Based on the six existing initiatives electrolysis is considered in all of them. The other technologies require more specific conditions, for example import terminals with good connections to waterways. These technologies are not presented in all existing initiatives and are therefore categorized as 'potential'.

2) Estimated importance of security of feed-in.

This means the importance for this entry customers to feed-in at anytime without constraints. Since for all entry customers delivering hydrogen is likely part of their primary business activity, their security of feed-in is perceived as important. For some of the electrolysis projects that aim to provide flexibility services to the electricity grid, or aim to valorize market opportunities in the short term electricity markets, it is even more important to have security to feed-in. For suppliers with storage facilities, security of feed-in might be slightly less relevant.

3) Indicative size of plant and profile characteristics.

The combination of the size of the plant a profile characteristics is important to consider: if a large plant injects with high variability, it has significantly more impact than a small one. Similar, a large plant that can partially steer its injection can reduce the flexibility need more significantly than a small plant that can steer its injection. The maximum and minimum feed-in as percentage of the average feed-in provides an indication of the degree of variability in the profile of the entry customer. Certainly, electrolysis based on wind and/or solar has a more variable injection profile than SMR and hydrogen carrier reconversion technologies. Biomass based hydrogen is adaptable on shorter timeframes, but is characterized by seasonal availability of biomass.

4) Impact flexibility needs on balancing requirements of the grid.

Due to their stable and adaptable nature, SMR and hydrogen carrier reconversion technologies are neutral on flexibility needs as long as the exit customers demand for baseload energy supply. Electrolysis and biomass gasification are characterized by respectively seconds/minute based and seasonal based profiles, which means that complementary flexibility from other parties is required. The size and timescale of the required flexibility depends on the size and security of feed-in characteristics of that particular project that wants to join the trading portfolio and connect to the grid.

Table 12: Overview of flexibility needs from entry customers.

Entry customers	Likelihood entry in regional grids	Importance security of feed-in	Indicative size of plant	Profile characteristics	Impact flexibility/ balancing requirement of the grid
Electrolysis (wind)	Likely	High	1 – 50 MW	Minute based variations, seasonal	Requires complementary flexibility
Electrolysis (solar)	Likely	High	1 – 25 MW	Minute based variations, seasonal	Requires complementary flexibility
SMR	Potential	High	>250 MW	Stable, but adaptable on market conditions	Neutral
Biomass gasification	Potential	High	10 – 50 MW	Seasonal, but adaptable on shorter timeframes	Requires seasonal complementary flexibility
Ammonia cracking	Potential	High	>250 MW	Stable, but adaptable on market conditions	Neutral
Vaporization liquid hydrogen	Potential	High	>100 MW	Stable, but adaptable on market conditions	Neutral

Table 13 Provides an overview of the key flexibility need characteristics from exit customers. These characteristics are similar to the entry characteristics, but differ per customer:

1) An estimated likelihood of their existence in hydrogen distribution grids.

Based on the expected willingness to pay for hydrogen, the industrial consumers are evaluated on their likelihood of entering regional hydrogen grids. The existing initiatives show, however, that also industries with relatively low willingness to pay and electrification options, such as the paper and food industry, are also present in these initiatives and considering hydrogen. For power plants, road transport and agriculture vehicles and the build environment, evaluation is based on respectively the size of these plants, small high-quality volumes and the political position.

2) Estimated importance of security of supply

The security of supply is important for all exit customers. However, zooming in greater detail shows differences in the financial impact between certain industries, which was used to base this indicative estimation on. For hydrogen in vehicles this really depends on the type and purpose of the vehicles and for buildings this is based on legal requirements to deliver heat even despite very low temperatures. For offtakers able to switch between different fuels (e.g. hydrogen and natural gas), the security of supply for the hydrogen might be less important, as long as there is still security of supply from the other fuel (e.g. natural gas).

3) Indicative size of plant and profile characteristics

Similar to the entry customers, size and profile characteristics are key to evaluate flexibility needs and balancing requirements of the grid. The size and flexibility of large scale power plants is so large that it is perceived hardly feasible to connect them at distribution level. They are ideally connected to the national infrastructure. The typical sizes of industrial offtakers are mainly based on the customer typologies developed in HyDelta 3 [7], obviously they can differ per individual plant. The profiles can roughly be differentiated between baseload consumption of continuous industrial processes (e.g. glass, ceramics, etc.) and more variable consumption of batchwise processes (e.g. paper, food, etc.) or a combination of both. In one of the existing initiatives the peaks of an asphalt plant were named as challenging to provide flexibility to. The demand of mobility is relatively so small compared to industry, that the variations might be neglectable if large scale industrial players are connected to the similar grid infrastructure.

4) Impact flexibility needs on balancing requirements of the grid

The table clearly shows that a lot of the most likely industrial exit customers require a stable baseload supply with a high degree of security. This might be a challenge if supply is primarily delivered by variable entry customers, such as electrolysis. The challenge might be even larger if relatively large consumers with variable consumption, such as a large food plant, should be supplied primarily via electrolysis. However, in the existing initiatives it was seen that also flexibility can be delivered by consumers. This will be analyzed in greater detail in chapter 3.2. Also solutions for significant consumption peaks, such as for asphalt plants and back-up power will be taken into account.

The built environment can require significant flexibility needs too, however, given the current political position on hydrogen in the built environment, these type of customers are not expected to be participating in these grids with significant exit volumes in at least the next decade.

Table 13: Overview of flexibility needs from exit customers [7].

Exit customers	Likelihood entry in regional grids	Importance security of supply	Indicative size of plant	Profile characteristics	Impact flexibility/ balancing requirement of the grid
Cement	Potential	Mid	4-11 MW	Continuous, baseload	Stable supply
Concrete	Potential	Mid	Unknown	Continuous, baseload	Stable supply
Asphalt	Potential	Mid	~2 MW	Peak power requirements	Peak supply flexibility
Chemicals	Likely	High	4-30 MW	Continuous, baseload, small variable part	Stable supply, flexible supply
Paper	Potential	Mid	~11 MW	Batchwise variations	flexible supply
Food	Potential	Mid	4-76 MW	Batchwise variations	flexible supply

Glass	Likely	High	27-50 MW	Baseload	Stable supply
Ceramics	Likely	High	4-15 MW	Baseload	Stable supply
Metal	Likely	Mid	Unknown	Baseload	Stable supply
Greenhouse	Potential	Mid	Unknown	Flexible E/H2 uptake CHP	None
Other industry	Potential	-	-	Baseload with variable part	Stable supply, flexible supply
Power plant (large)	Low	High	500-2000 MW	Flexible power supply	Large scale storage and peak supply
Back-up power (small)	Potential	High	1-20 MW	Flexible power supply	Small scale storage and peak supply
Agriculture	Low	Mid	Small	Seasonal with daily variations	Seasonal supply, hourly flexibility
Mobility	Potential	Mid/low	Small	Week and daily variation	Hourly flexibility
Buildings	Low (short term)	High	Depends on # houses	Seasonal with hourly variations	Seasonal supply

Next to the characteristics in Table 12 and Table 13, all entry and exit parties face the risk of disruptions in their process or assets being down. The larger the scale production/consumption, the larger the potential impact of disruptions and downtime of these customers. The flexibility and balancing requirements to anticipate on such events should be considered as well. It should be noted that for electrolysis the risk of a full system being down is relatively small, due to their modular designs.

B. Detailed information on market flexibility options

Flexibility of electrolysis depending on regulation, subsidy and electricity grid services

Usage of grey electricity in subsidized electrolysis

Within Dutch subsidy schemes for hydrogen production via electrolysis, a clear distinction exists between the technical capability to use grid electricity and the conditions under which subsidies are granted. Electrolysis are technologically agnostic regarding the origin of electricity and can therefore operate on both renewable and fossil-based power. However, subsidy frameworks primarily incentivize the production of renewable hydrogen rather than the mere operation of electrolysis capacity.

Under the ‘Opschaling Waterstof via Elektrolyse’ (OWE) scheme, the use of grid electricity is permitted. In practice, this implies that the electricity mix may contain a grey component. At the same time, the hydrogen produced must comply with minimum greenhouse gas reduction thresholds which are typically around 70% compared to fossil benchmarks. Consequently, only the share of hydrogen production that meets these emission reduction criteria is effectively considered eligible within the subsidy framework. While the scheme allows some flexibility in electricity sourcing, it implicitly targets

renewable hydrogen output. In contrast, operational support schemes such as the SDE++ apply stricter conditions. These schemes subsidize only the “unprofitable top” of renewable hydrogen production. Hydrogen produced using grey electricity does not qualify for subsidy payments, regardless of the technical capability of the installation. This creates a clear financial distinction between renewable and non-renewable production pathway. It must be noted that these subsidies do not restrict on the usage of grey electricity if the system requires it for balancing. However, grey electricity is not subsidized. Hence, running an electrolyser becomes more expensive. Therefore, this has impact on the business case of the electrolyser operator.

Innovation-oriented instruments such as the ‘Demonstratie Energie- en Klimaatinnovatie’ (DEI+) adopt a different approach. These schemes focus on technological development and demonstration of CO₂ reduction potential. As a result, the use of grey electricity is generally permitted within projects, provided that the overall system demonstrates meaningful emission reductions and innovation outcomes. In this context, the carbon intensity of electricity is less strictly regulated than in operational subsidy schemes. On the demand side, schemes aimed at stimulating industrial hydrogen uptake such as the ‘Subsidieregeling voor de transitie naar klimaatneutrale industrie met waterstof’ (STIHWI), typically define eligibility in terms of renewable hydrogen consumption. This implies that hydrogen produced using grey electricity does not qualify for demand-side support, even if the production installation itself has received investment subsidies.

In summary, Dutch subsidy policy does not generally prohibit the use of grey electricity in electrolyzers. However, financial support is predominantly linked to the production or use of renewable hydrogen. This results in a policy framework in which grey electricity can be used operationally, but is economically disincentivized because it does not, or only partially, contribute to subsidized output. This does indicate that grey electricity can be used for flexibility services, although it will not be subsidized.

Considerations of electricity and hydrogen grid services for electrolysis

Moreover, some electrolyzers want to play a role at electricity balancing markets. Electrolyser operator can not assign capacity for both electricity grid and hydrogen grid services at the same time. Hence, also here business case considerations and value stacking strategies will play a role. This will impact the degree in which electrolyzers will be utilized for hydrogen grid services, but their actual decisions are unclear due to uncertainty in the balancing market prices and revenues for both types of services.

Considerations for flexibility options on the exit side

Energy system related flexibility

Table 4 provides an overview of the identified energy system related flexibility options on the exit side. These are often technologies that provide the option for dual fuel usage or local storage of energy at the exit location, such as hybrid boilers, hybrid combined heat and power (CHP) installations or local storage. Hydrogen boilers have a cold start-up of 1-5 hours and are able to ramp up or down in the order of minutes and switch between fuels in the order of seconds. Therefore, these provide excellent flexibility options. If a dual fuel burner is installed in the boiler hydrogen can be blended or switched with natural gas streams behind the meter. Also, a hydrogen boiler can be combined with an industrial heat pump to be able to switch between electricity and hydrogen. Finally, hydrogen boilers can be combined with heat buffers to decouple energy consumption from the primary process, at least for a certain timeframe depending on the storage capacity. It should be noted that these boilers and CHPs are often used for low and medium temperature heat processes, such as in the paper and food industry. However, typically these processes can also fully be electrified. Therefore, it is uncertain to

what degree such customers will be present in hydrogen grids and able to provide this type of flexibility.

For industries with limited alternatives for hydrogen, such as the glass, ceramics and decentral metal industries, the flames from the burners are in direct contact with the end product. This means that the flame characteristics, which change if (varying) blends of natural gas and hydrogen would be used, do impact the quality and characteristics of the products (e.g. glass, bricks, metals, etc.) produced. Therefore, it seems not likely that these type of exit customers will be able to run their processes by dual fuels.

For chemical industries the options for energy system related flexibility differs per factory. In one of the initiatives there was a chemical company that was able to blend hydrogen with natural gas behind the meter flexibly with variations from 0 to 20%. Also for chemical companies using hydrogen as feedstock in their processes already, it could be an option to blend in variable streams of green hydrogen in the existing ones. However, also this option will be process dependent.

Primary process related flexibility

Table 5 provides an overview of the potential primary process related flexibility per sector. The two main categories are continuous processes that can increase or decrease the output of the plants and batch processes that can reschedule batches to increase or decrease the energy consumption during that period. Finally, there are some exit customers with more specific process and flexibility options.

The continuous processes, often seen in concrete, chemical, glass and ceramic sectors are designed to run on baseload and are often hard to adjust. In principle production can be increased as long as these processes are not already running on full capacity (which is often the case) and if input resources are sufficiently available. Decreasing production might be easier, but reduces the profitability of the plant and could cause expiring of input resources. Adjusting these processes takes time (for example due to cooling of ovens in the glass and ceramic sectors) and comes often with significant costs [2].

Batching processes, often seen in concrete, paper and food sectors, provide the option to reschedule batches such that more or less energy is used, depending on the batch activity. Depending on the duration of the batches adjustments can be made within a range of a couple of hours [2].

Next to these two main processes, there are sectors with more specific flexibility options. The first are greenhouses which can adjust their heating on short terms without significant consequences for the production, logistics fleets that are not used 24/7 and can perform smart charging (despite volumes likely being very small) and specific hydrogen tube filling businesses that can be flexible on when they fill their tubes. Also this latter option is likely relatively small in volume compared to industrial hydrogen consumption.

Merit order and cost indications for market flexibility options

But which ones will be prioritized if all or multiple of these options would be available? Market theory assumes that the flexibility options with the lowest costs will be prioritized first, in order to balance supply and demand cost effectively.

In liquid markets this is determined via the merit order principle: the flexibility provider with the lowest marginal costs to deliver additional unit (e.g. MWh) of flexibility in the required direction (i.e. ramping up or down), is the most cost effective choice to provide the flexibility. However, in archetypes 1-3 it is not certain that there will be a liquid flexibility market, due to the potential limited number of actors. Also, specific designs of balancing instruments and contracts can lead to different measures for

prioritization: for example it could be that a trading party decides to contract one connected party to provide flexibility against its expected integral costs for flexibility provision. In such a case the lowest integral flexibility provision costs do determines which flexibility option is chosen, instead of the marginal costs. Another option could be that the trading party contracts a prioritization beforehand with its connected parties, differing in security of supply and trade agreements. Hence, the actual activation of flexibility options depends on the detailed designs of balancing instruments and contracts. Therefore, this chapter is just to be seen as an high-over indication of the costs involved per flexibility option.

Table 14 provides an indicative overview of the marginal costs of the flexibility options. Flexibility is distinguished between upward and downward flexibility. Upward flexibility is demanded when demand exceeds supply at a certain moment. This can be provided by increasing injection or reducing consumption. Downward flexibility is demanded when supply exceeds demand at a certain moment. This can be provided by decreasing injection or increasing consumption.

The information in this table is prone to a high level of uncertainty, as it depends heavily on energy prices, contractual agreements and industrial specific characteristics. Also the party who is eligible for these costs depends on the exact design of the balancing instruments and contracts (see chapter **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**), likely this should be the causer(s) of the imbalance. However, still a couple of insights can be given:

1) Increasing hydrogen injection for upward flexibility

For hydrogen feed-in to increase compared to the planned feed-in, it requires more fuel input than originally planned and purchased. Obviously, these options are only available if feed-in capacity was not used already to the full extend. For electrolysis and SMR this means that more electricity or natural gas needs to be purchased in those markets and therefore marginal costs depend primarily on the prices in those markets at that specific time. For biomass gasification and reconversion of hydrogen carriers, also more input resources are needed than planned, however, as these technologies are often foreseen to be coupled to a biomass or hydrogen carrier storage facility, costs of for these additional resources might be less dependent on short term markets. Another option is withdrawing hydrogen from a decentralized hydrogen pressure storage facility, as long as stored hydrogen is available at that moment. Since the hydrogen is released by the difference in pressure, no significant marginal costs are expected.

2) Decreasing hydrogen injection for downward flexibility

For hydrogen feed-in to decrease compared to the planned feed-in, it results likely in less profits for the entry party and that potentially supply agreements are not met. The latter is especially something to consider when the causer is not a consumer that is supplied by the downward flexibility provider. Hence, the marginal costs depend on the missed profits and eventual penalties for the entry party, which primarily depend on contractual agreements.

3) Decreasing hydrogen consumption for upward flexibility

The impact on exit customers providing upward flexibility differs for energy system related flexibility options and primary process related flexibility options. Hybrid consumers can decrease their hydrogen usage and instead using another fuel (e.g. electricity or natural gas). The marginal costs to do so depend on the additional costs of using the other fuel and towards what extend the purchased hydrogen can be cancelled without any costs. It seems likely that arrangements for this will be made in contracts including hybrid consumers and entry parties who are in need of a lot of flexibility, such as electrolyzers.

Typically more costs are involved for industries that adapt their primary processes [2], where typically rescheduling certain batches has lower impact on profitability than reducing or stopping the production in continuous processes [2]. This directly impacts the turnover of a plant.

There are three remaining exit parties who are expected to decrease their hydrogen consumption to a certain extent with barely marginal costs involved, namely industrial customers with heat buffers, greenhouses and hydrogen tube filling stations.

4) Increasing hydrogen consumption for downward flexibility

Also for downward flexibility, the impact on exit customers differs for energy system related and primarily process related flexibility options. Obviously for both types capacity should be available to consume more hydrogen than initially planned. For example, if hybrid consumers already were consuming their full capacity with hydrogen, it is not possible to increase further. Increasing consumption for hybrid consumers would mean that more hydrogen is used than initially planned and less of another fuel, the impact on their marginal costs likely depends on contract arrangements. If not in place, then additional hydrogen needs to be purchased and alternative fuel purchases needs to be sold again.

For primary process related flexibility similar issues are seen as discussed before. However, increasing continuous processes might in some cases have less impact on the turnover than decreasing production. However, still these processes are hard to adapt and often are running on the maximum desired capacity already.

Similar insights can be taken into account for heat buffers, greenhouses and tube filling stations as for the decrease of consumption. Another option for increasing the consumption temporarily is decentral hydrogen storage in pressure tanks, of which the marginal costs involve some electricity purchasing costs.

Table 14: Overview of indicative merit order characteristics of different flexibility options. Note that these numbers are just indications and the actual marginal costs for parties might heavily depend on contractual agreements.

Type	Flexibility option	Upward marginal costs	Cost depending on	Downward marginal costs	Costs depending on	Timescale
Entry	Electrolysis	0-300 EUR/MWh	Electricity costs	0-300 EUR/MWh	Hydrogen margin/penalty	Seconds-minutes
	SMR	0-300 EUR/MWh	Natural gas costs	0-300 EUR/MWh	Hydrogen margin/penalty	Minute
	Biomass gasification	0-300 EUR/MWh	Biomass costs	0-300 EUR/MWh	Hydrogen margin/penalty	Minute
	Cracking/vaporization	0-300 EUR/MWh	H2 carrier costs	0-300 EUR/MWh	Hydrogen margin/penalty	Minute
	Gaseous H2 storage	~0 EUR/MWh	No costs included	*	*	Seconds
Exit – system	Hybrid H2/NG offtake	0-300 EUR/MWh	Natural gas costs	100-400 EUR/MWh	Hydrogen costs	Seconds-minutes
	Hybrid E/H2 offtake	0-300 EUR/MWh	Electricity costs	100-400 EUR/MWh	Hydrogen costs	Seconds-minutes

	Gaseous H2 storage	*	*	0-30 EUR/MWh	Electricity compression	Seconds
	Heat buffer, greenhouse, tube filling	Very low	Barely costs included	Very low	Barely costs included	Seconds-minutes
Exit – process	Rescheduling	50-500 EUR/MWh	Turnover	50-500 EUR/MWh	Turnover	Hours-weeks
	Decreasing / increasing	800-8000 EUR/MWh	Turnover, inputs	800-8000 EUR/MWh	Overcapacity, additional stock	>12 hours-weeks
	Production stop	800-8000 EUR/MWh	Turnover, inputs	N/A	N/A	Days-weeks

**Storage injection and withdrawal can only be decreased if injection/withdrawal was already planned.*

As discussed at the start of this chapter, next to the marginal costs it is also relevant to look into the integral, levelized flexibility costs for the flexibility options. Especially for archetype 1-3 grid with a limited number of players, it seems likely that trading parties will specify in their trading contracts degrees of firmness between connected parties and specific arrangements for who will deliver the flexibility if certain disturbances take place. Especially for this latter aspect the integral costs might be more relevant than the marginal costs: if back-up is contracted for a longer period, it seems likely that the party that can provide this for the lowest integral costs will be chosen. For industrial consumers, example significant, this would require significant investments in over-capacity, if they want to provide downward flexibility on a general basis. This seems not very likely. This seems more likely for assets with relatively low investment costs, short reaction times and the more often the back up is required the more important also the marginal costs become.

Another consideration could be to contract upward and downward flexibility for specific timeframes (e.g. in order of hours, days or weeks). An advantage of this is that when certain entry or exit parties expect to have spare capacity free during a specific moment, this opportunity could deliver flexibility possibly against lower cost for a specific period.

C. Technical tools for the DSO: incremental valves and storage

Distributed hydrogen storage

Definition

Hydrogen storage refers to the temporary containment of hydrogen that can later be released back into the distribution network when needed. In the context of a regional hydrogen distribution grid, storage provides operational flexibility by allowing the system to decouple hydrogen supply from hydrogen demand over time.

In this study, the focus is placed exclusively on compressed hydrogen gas storage as a technical solution for system balancing in a regional distribution grid. Other hydrogen storage technologies such as liquid hydrogen storage, metal hydride storage, and chemical hydrogen carriers are not considered in detail.

Storage allows the system to physically absorb excess hydrogen or supply additional hydrogen during periods of imbalance. This makes storage an important technical tool for the DSO when managing deviations between injections and withdrawals in the network. Storage can therefore support system

balancing, particularly in situations where linepack flexibility is insufficient or where supply and demand fluctuations occur over longer periods.

Hydrogen storage can be installed at strategic locations along the distribution pipeline, depending on where operational flexibility is most beneficial for the system. Typical locations include near hydrogen suppliers, near large consumers, or at intermediate points within the network where balancing actions may have the greatest effect. By placing storage at these locations, the DSO can respond more effectively to local imbalances between supply and demand and support stable pressure conditions in the network. Likewise, it is important at which side of the flange the storage is positioned (behind customer connection or a dedicated grid connection) and what the exact business model and ownership of the storage facility is (e.g. shaving price spikes, capturing value from price spreads, contracted by DSO or even operated by the DSO, etc.). This chapter focuses solely on the technical characteristics.

In general, two typical configurations of hydrogen storage can be distinguished based on the working pressure of the storage system:

1. Storage operating at the same pressure as the pipeline (8–16 bar)

In this configuration, the hydrogen storage system operates within the same pressure range as the distribution pipeline, typically between 8 and 16 bar. Because the storage pressure matches the pipeline pressure, hydrogen can flow between the storage facility and the network with minimal additional equipment.

The main advantage of this configuration is its simplicity of operation. Hydrogen can be stored when the pressure in the network increases and released when the pressure decreases, using relatively simple control valves. In many cases, no compression equipment is required because the pressure difference between the network and the storage system is small.

This type of storage can function as a buffer directly connected to the pipeline, allowing it to quickly absorb excess hydrogen or supply hydrogen when demand increases. As a result, storage operating at pipeline pressure is particularly useful for short-term balancing and pressure stabilization within the distribution grid.

However, because the storage pressure is relatively low, the energy density is limited, meaning that larger storage volumes may be required to store significant amounts of hydrogen.

Figure 6. Example compressed gas storage: industrial gas storage (left) and tube trailer skids (right)

2. Storage operating at higher pressure (350–700 bar)

A second configuration involves storing hydrogen at much higher pressures, typically between 350 and 700 bar. These pressure levels are commonly used in compressed hydrogen storage systems and hydrogen refuelling infrastructure.

In this configuration, hydrogen must be compressed before entering the storage system, which requires additional equipment such as compressors, pressure control systems, and safety devices. When hydrogen is needed in the network, it must be decompressed or regulated before being injected back into the distribution pipeline.

Although this configuration is technically more complex, it provides a significant advantage in terms of storage capacity. By storing hydrogen at much higher pressure, a large quantity of hydrogen can be stored within a relatively small physical space.

High-pressure storage can therefore provide larger balancing capacity compared with pipeline-pressure storage. It is particularly useful in situations where hydrogen production or consumption varies significantly, or where large amounts of hydrogen need to be stored temporarily.

However, the need for compressors and additional equipment also means that this type of storage involves higher investment costs, energy consumption, and operational complexity.

Figure 7. Example type IV hydrogen storage vessels. A fully composite tanks featuring a non-metallic polymer inner liner (such as HDPE or Nylon) reinforced with an exterior carbon fiber or thermoplastic wrapping.

How the storage works for system balancing

Hydrogen storage in a distribution network acts as a buffer to maintain stable pressure within the system. The operation of the storage is closely linked to the network pressure levels and the predefined pressure zones (green, yellow, orange, red) discussed earlier.

Filling the storage

When the network pressure rises into the upper orange zone, it indicates that supply is temporarily exceeding demand. At this point:

- The storage valve opens, allowing hydrogen to flow from the pipeline into the storage system.
- For high-pressure storage systems, the compressor also starts running, pressurizing the hydrogen as it enters the storage tank.
- By absorbing excess hydrogen, the storage system reduces pressure in the network, helping it return to the yellow zone, which represents a normal or mild deviation.
- Once the pressure stabilizes within the upper yellow zone, the valve closes, stopping further hydrogen inflow into storage and in case of high pressure storage, the compressor stops.

This operation ensures that pressure does not exceed safe limits and prevents overpressure conditions in the network.

Releasing hydrogen

Conversely, when the network pressure drops into the lower orange zone, it indicates that demand temporarily exceeds supply. In this situation:

- The storage valve opens, allowing hydrogen to flow from the storage system back into the network.
- This injection of hydrogen helps increase the network pressure and supports continuous supply to connected consumers.
- Once the pressure returns to the lower yellow zone, the valve closes, stopping further hydrogen release.

By providing additional hydrogen during low-pressure periods, the storage system prevents under pressure conditions and ensures safe and reliable operation of the network.

Considerations for high-pressure storage with compressors

For storage systems operating at higher pressures (e.g., 350–700 bar), a compressor is required to inject hydrogen into the storage tank. In these cases:

- The start-up time of the compressor must be considered, as the system cannot instantly store or release hydrogen.
- The ramp-up rate of the compressor defines how quickly hydrogen can be injected or withdrawn.
- These specifications are typically defined during the compressor selection process. For example, a compressor may be designed to reach full operational conditions within 1–2 minutes.

Even with the additional delay from the compressor start-up, high-pressure storage provides larger capacity and longer-term flexibility compared with pipeline-pressure storage. Proper integration of the compressor control system ensures that the storage can still respond effectively to pressure deviations in the network.

Proof of concept

In this section, we demonstrate the mechanism of a distribution grid with compressed hydrogen storage for network where the balancing response time is within minutes.

Example:

The network consists of two suppliers (each with a 20 MW PEM electrolyzer producing 4000 Nm³/h of hydrogen) and four consumers (each with flow demand of 2000 Nm³/h). The pipeline has a length of 5 km and a diameter of DN100. The storage is located in the middle of the network.

Figure 8. Example hydrogen network with 2 suppliers and 4 consumers.

Scenario: one of the electrolyzers trips, causing a supply imbalance of 4000 Nm³/h. Consequently, the system pressure decreases as the demand exceeds the available supply.

Results:

The equation to calculate the storage size has been provided in [1] Section 3.2. The required hydrogen volume to accommodate the imbalance from minutes to 1 hour is:

$$V_{\text{req}} = 4000 \text{ Nm}^3$$

Applying the mid-level flexibility rule, the working volume becomes:

$$V_{\text{work}} = 2 \times 4000 = 8000 \text{ Nm}^3$$

This volume is equivalent to 712 kg of hydrogen. For a hydrogen storage system with a minimum pressure of 8 bar, the corresponding storage tank size are depending on the maximum pressure:

Pressure (barg)	Tank Volume (m ³)
16	1251
350	31
700	18

If the storage also needs to cover a longer-term imbalance (e.g., 8 hours), the required tank volume can simply be multiplied by the imbalance time in hours. Single tube trailers carry approximately 500-1000 kg of hydrogen, depending on the pressure and container material. The largest tank volumes for gaseous hydrogen transport are currently 26 m³.

Estimated cost ranges for hydrogen storage options

Hydrogen storage can be implemented in different configurations depending on the network requirements, available space, and desired flexibility. Estimated cost for each solutions are presented below:

1. Storage at pipeline pressure

Factor	Description
Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)	Relatively low. Tanks are moderate-pressure vessels; no compressors are required. Installation is simpler and often requires less land.
Operational Expenditure (OPEX)	Low. Energy consumption is minimal since no compression is needed. Maintenance is primarily valves, pressure monitoring, and safety systems.
Complexity	Low. Integration into the pipeline is straightforward; storage control is mainly valve operation.
Capacity vs Space	Limited. Because the pressure is low, the volume needed to store significant hydrogen is large. Suitable for short-term or local balancing rather than long-term storage.

Cost Element	Estimated Range	Notes
Storage Tanks & Installation	€ 400 – € 1,000 per kg H ₂	Depends on vessel materials and certification
Site Preparation & Piping	€ 50,000 – € 250,000	Small to medium project site

Control & Safety Systems	€ 50,000 – € 150,000	Includes pressure sensors, PLC, valves
--------------------------	----------------------	--

2. High pressure compressed gas storage

Factor	Description
Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)	High. High pressure tanks (often Type IV composite) are more expensive. Compressors, control systems, and safety devices increase total cost.
Operational Expenditure (OPEX)	Moderate to high. Compressors consume energy during pressurization. Regular maintenance is needed for high pressure systems and valves.
Complexity	High. Integration requires careful control of pressure, start-up procedures for compressors, and safety monitoring. Operational planning is more sophisticated.
Capacity vs Space	High. A smaller footprint can store much more hydrogen compared with low-pressure storage. Suitable for medium-term balancing and areas with space constraints.

Cost Element	Estimated Range	Notes
High-Pressure Storage Tanks	€ 800 – € 2,000 per kg H ₂	Varies by tank type (Type III vs Type IV composites)
Compressors	€ 50,000 – € 250,000	Depends on size, technology, speed
Support Systems (valves, safety, controls)	€ 50,000 – € 150,000	Regulators, monitoring, PLC
Piping & Site Works	€ 100,000 – € 500,000	Foundation, cabling, interlocks

Incremental valve at the connection point

Definition

An incremental valve is a control valve installed at the connection point between the hydrogen distribution network and a connected party, such as a supplier or a consumer. Unlike an emergency shut-off valve, which is either fully open or fully closed, an incremental valve allows the hydrogen flow to be adjusted gradually in small steps. This enables the DSO to control the amount of hydrogen entering or leaving the network without immediately interrupting the connection.

The main purpose of incremental valves in this context is not to redirect flows within the network, but rather to limit injections and withdrawals in a controlled manner. By doing so, the DSO can respond to operational constraints while avoiding abrupt disconnection of suppliers or consumers and preventing ripple effects.

How the valve works

An incremental valve regulates hydrogen flow by adjusting the opening position of the valve. When the valve is fully open, hydrogen can flow freely between the network and the connected facility. As

the valve gradually closes, the opening becomes smaller, increasing resistance to the flow and reducing the amount of hydrogen passing through the connection.

The adjustment can be performed manually or automatically through the network's control system. In most cases, the valve is connected to a remote monitoring and control system, allowing the DSO to modify the valve position from the control centre.

The valve position is typically expressed as a percentage of the maximum opening. For example:

- **100% open** – the connection operates at its full allowed capacity
- **25-50-75% open** – the flow is partially restricted
- **0% open** – the connection is fully closed

By changing the valve position in small increments, the DSO can gradually reduce the flow rate rather than making sudden changes.

Figure 9. Schematic of a flow control system (flow transmitter, controller and control valve)

Typical configuration at connection point

Incremental valves are typically installed as part of a connection station between the hydrogen network and a connected party. This station may include several components that allow safe and controlled operation of the connection.

A typical configuration may include:

- **Isolation valves**, used to completely shut off the connection during maintenance or emergency situations.
- **Incremental control valves**, used to gradually regulate the hydrogen flow.
- **Pressure regulators**, ensuring that the pressure delivered to the connected party (demand side) remains within acceptable limits.
- **Flow measurement** equipment, which monitors the amount of hydrogen entering or leaving the network.
- **Safety devices**, such as pressure relief systems and emergency shut-off mechanisms.

In this configuration, the incremental valve functions as the primary operational control element that the DSO can adjust during normal system operation.

This configuration usually is installed inside the box which located either owned by the connected party (gatekeeper/control station) or owned by DSO (pressure safety station).

Figure 10. Installation box at the connection points where multiple equipment are installed.

Workflow mechanism

The incremental control valve can be either manually controlled via telemetry from the control system room to provide a setpoint flow rate, or automatically controlled based on network pressure via a programmable logic controller (PLC). The automatic workflow is explained in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Example workflow of incremental valve that automatically reduce valve opening based downstream network pressure.

Proof of concept

In this section, we demonstrate the mechanism of a distribution grid with and without an incremental valve for network where the balancing response time is within minutes.

Example:

The network consists of two suppliers (each with a 20 MW PEM electrolyzer producing 4000 Nm³/h of hydrogen) and four consumers (each with flow demand of 2000 Nm³/h). The pipeline has a length of 5 km and a diameter of DN100.

Figure 12. Example hydrogen network with 2 suppliers and 4 consumers.

Base Result:

Figure 13. Simulation results of the network: flowrate in Nm³/h (top) and pressure in bar (bottom). Total pressure drop is 2.65 bar

Scenario: one of the electrolyzers trips, causing a supply imbalance of 4000 Nm³/h. Consequently, the system pressure decreases as the demand exceeds the available supply.

Results:

- **Case 1:** Without incremental valve (only safety valve)
 The simulation results is shown in Figure 14. When Electrolyzer 1 trips at minute 5, the system pressure decreases. Once the pressure at the consumer connection (2,3, and 4) reaches 8 bar, the safety valve is activated, closing the valve. At this point, only Consumer 1 remains active. As the system enters an overproduction condition, the pressure begins to rise again until another safety valve on the supplier side is triggered when the pressure reaches 16 bar. This situation is undesirable, as it indicates that the network becomes unstable, causing a ripple effect across all assets

Figure 14. Simulation results of the network with only safety valves: pressure (top) and flowrate (bottom)

- Case 2:** With an incremental valve in addition to the safety valve
 Another case considers the same scenario, but with the network equipped with incremental valves for Consumers 2, 3, and 4. Consumer 1 is assigned a higher priority due to a different contract with the DSO. The incremental valves operate based on pressure thresholds: when the pressure drops below 8.5 bar, the flow rate is reduced by half; if the pressure further decreases below 8.3 bar, the flow rate is reduced again by half. The simulation results for this case are presented in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Simulation results of the network with incremental valve: pressure (top) and flowrate (bottom)

As can be seen from the simulation, the ripple effect does not occur, and the network remains capable of operating in a stable manner within the specified pressure range (8-16 bar). During the subsequent balancing hours, the network pressure can be restored to its original level by procuring additional hydrogen from another supplier to compensate for the loss caused by the Electrolyzer 1 event.

Both cases demonstrate the benefit of incorporating incremental valves in the network, particularly when the response time is short. However, the installation of incremental valves should be coordinated with the connected parties. For example, consumers equipped with incremental valves must be able to continue their production processes even when the flow rate is reduced by the valve. This should be assessed on a case-by-case basis, depending on the type of consumer.

Estimated cost ranges for incremental valve

An incremental valve at a hydrogen network connection is typically a modulating control valve with remote actuation and integrated pressure/flow measurement, connected to a SCADA or DCS control system.

Note: Actual costs depend on valve size, pressure rating, automation level, safety compliance (e.g., explosion protection), and project location.

The tables below are indicative ranges often used in early engineering planning.

Cost Element	Estimated Range	Notes
Valve unit	€10,000 – €40,000	Modulating control valve, actuator, valve positioner
Instrumentation & control	€5,000 – €25,000	Pressure/flow sensor, local control panel, communication interface (SCADA/DCS)
Installation & commissioning	€5,000 – €25,000	Mechanical installation, electrical/cabling, commissioning & testing

D. Description of the concept set of balancing instruments

In this appendix a brief, but more detailed description is provided for the balancing instruments and supportive instruments included in this report. There will be focused on the general implications of applying the instrument in Archetype 1-3 grids and what is required to implement the instrument successfully.

From balancing functions to a set of instruments

It should be noted that there is no balancing regime or descriptive regulation in place yet. This means that it is yet to be determined how a balancing regime for archetype 1-3 grids will be designed. This involves a significant more extensive process and engagement of a significant larger group of stakeholders than was present in this study. Therefore, this chapter should be interpreted as an exploratory assessment in which the balancing functions defined in phase 1 of this research are translated into a potential set of balancing instruments (5.1). For this set of instruments requirements are explored (5.2). The goal is to provide an first view on what balancing in these grids involves, what is required and what challenges might be involved. This is a preliminary step for a more extensive design process. The reader should therefore realize that an unlimited number of other balancing regime designs will be possible.

In phase 1 a set of key functions defined that should be in place in every balancing system. This is the starting point to define which potential balancing instrument would be required for archetype 1-3 grids. Table 15 provides an overview of the 11 balancing functions.

Table 15: Overview of balancing function defined in phase 1 [1]

#	Function name	Indicative time scale
F1	Investment and maintenance of hydrogen infrastructure	>Year ahead
F2	Assignment of transport capacity to trading parties	Yearly until hourly
F3	Connecting feed-in and offtake - nominations	Day ahead
F4	Nomination review and confirmation	Day ahead
F5	Measurement and data management	5-15 minutes
F6	Maintaining transport capacity in real-time	5-15 minutes
F7	Real-time portfolio balancing	5-15 minutes
F8	Maintaining system integrity real-time	15 minutes until seconds
F9	Delivery – sales and purchases	The moment of delivery
F10	Allocation and correction	Day after
F11	Flexibility services	15 minutes until seconds

An assessment was performed to define for every function which instrument was needed to perform the function. Some instruments were capable of performing multiple functions, and some functions were relevant for multiple instruments. After multiple discussions about the set of instruments, it was recognized that some instruments are directly steering the physical assets delivering flexibility for balancing (e.g. flexibility agreements in trading contracts), while others are just passive in terms of steering, but provide information to support the balancing process (e.g. nominations and trading platforms). Therefore, it was decided to recategorize the identified instruments into ‘balancing instruments’ and ‘supportive instruments’. The instruments are presented within this categorization.

1. Balancing instruments

Trading agreements

Trading contracts are the commercial agreements between trading party and connected party, defining supply, flexibility obligations, volumes and response characteristics. This is the core mechanism for portfolio balancing in archetypes 1-3 grids. Contracts with different parties must assure that the whole portfolio remains in balance under most conditions.

Flex contract

Flex contracts are contracted flexibility of assets (e.g. electrolysers, storage, flexible consumption assets) by the DSO, to adjust within defined response times. Connected parties obtain a fee to reserve capacity of these assets to perform system balancing actions on signals of the DSO. This can be a cost effective way of providing system balancing actions if certain connected parties have spare flexibility capacity, and if the DSO has limited alternative flexibility for system balancing actions.

DSO managed flexibility (linepack and/or storage)

If the DSO owns flexibility options themselves, such as linepack in pipelines and/or decentralized storage assets, they could be used as short-term buffer (seconds–minutes). When assignable, causes can be billed for such interventions. However, in phase 1 it became clear that the flexibility by linepack in hydrogen distribution grids might be very limited. Optionally storage could be owned by DSO if no sufficient other flexibility options available in the grid, if regulatory accepted. Given the foreseen flexibility requirements in these grids, it seems likely that in some cases flexibility options from market parties might be limited.

Restrictions (non-firm)

If the DSO has agreed on the authority to temporarily limit feed-in/offtake/transport under interruptible/non-firm arrangements in transport contracts, these may be used as system balancing instrument. Given the scarce flexibility in archetype 1-3 grids, these type of agreements might be desirable to limit the number of integrity actions required.

Emergency actions

Emergency or integrity actions are the last resort system balancing action if no other measures can be taken to remain grid integrity. These emergency physical measures could include (partially) shutting valves of connected parties. The option to perform last resort integrity actions is always desirable in gas networks. Due to the potentially low flexibility in archetype 1-3 grids, these are even more important.

2. Supportive instruments

Transport contract

Transport contracts assign transport rights to trading parties. These rights can be firm, non-firm or interruptible. In archetype 1 these are mainly administrative as there is only one direction of transport, while in archetypes 2 and 3 bilateral flows can exist. In archetype 3 transport rights are divided over multiple trading parties. Especially the agreements on firmness level are preconditional to use restrictions as system balancing mechanism.

Nominations

Nominations are forecasts/schedules of location specific feed-in, offtake and trades performed by the trading party and communicated with the DSO such that the combined overview can be shared with all the trading parties. They can be made for example on 15 or 60 minute granularity and shared a day before the planned activities. Nominations become relevant from archetype 3 as then multiple trading parties are in place and their combination of portfolio's should be in balance. In archetypes 1-2 the single trading party has the overview itself. At that stage there is no need to communicate this with the DSO, as the DSO will just measure what happens in the grid and intervene with system balancing actions when appropriate. Note that nomination systems in the existing electricity and natural gas systems are quite extensive, for decentral hydrogen grids the minimum effective system will be most desirable.

Imbalance signals & renominations

Near-real-time signals of portfolio/system imbalance enabling corrective action and renominations. Hence, there is a strong link with the nomination process. Similarly, this becomes relevant when multiple trading parties are present and therefore primarily from Archetype 3.

Transport capacity trading platform

Platform for secondary trading of short-term transport rights between trading parties. Also this instrument is only relevant as long as multiple trading parties are in place (archetype 3). It is probably

more a 'nice-to-have' instrument that can deliver most value when a liquid number of trading parties and scarce number of trading rights exist in the grid.

Flexibility services

Flexibility services between trading parties refer to voluntary bilateral or multilateral agreements where one trading party provides short-term supply or demand adjustments to another trading party to help them maintain their portfolio balance. This is only applicable for situation with multiple trading parties (archetype 3). Similar to the transport capacity trading platform, this is more a 'nice-to-have' as flexibility can and will be exchanged between portfolio's when multiple trading parties are in place. The added value of designing pre-defined services and conditions can benefit the competition and efficiency of the market, as long as a liquid number of trading parties and scarcity exist in the grid.

Reflection on the set of instruments

The applicability of the balancing instruments differ on the archetype and number of trading parties in the regional hydrogen grid. Archetypes 1 and 2 are seen to be quite similar in the balancing instruments that they require. Portfolio balancing in archetypes 1 and 2 is expected to be primarily arranged by the trading contracts between the trading party and connecting parties. System balancing in those grids can be done by arranging different firmness levels, interruptible conditions in trading contracts and integrity/emergency actions. Besides that flex contracts can be closed with connected parties if they are able to offer cost effective flexibility options for system balancing actions, or the DSO can utilize linepack or storage owned by themselves. Given the expected scarcity of flexibility in archetype 1 and 2 grids it seems likely that all these system balancing options need to be available in the set of instruments, despite that likely not all instruments will be used in every grid.

When multiple trading parties are present (archetype 3) nomination, renominations and imbalance signals become relevant to balance the combined portfolios of trading parties. Transport capacity trading platforms and flexibility services could deliver added value in allocating and exchanging transport rights and flexibility between the trading parties more effectively, but only when a larger number of trading parties, scarcity and a liquid market is in place. Therefore, a consideration is to be made what to do with these types of instruments: 1) not include them, 2) activate them when specific conditions are met, or 3) include them in such a way that they cannot harm the system.